

A photograph of a forest with sunlight filtering through the trees, creating a warm, golden glow. The sun is positioned in the upper center, casting long, vertical rays of light through the dense canopy of tall, thin trees. The ground is covered in a thick layer of green and brown vegetation, with dappled sunlight hitting the forest floor.

Agroforestry and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review and Technical Guidance

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart
Agricultural Practices

June 30, 2025

About the Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

WORKING GROUP	CHAIRPERSON	PRIMARY AFFILIATION	EMAIL
Agroforestry	Dr. Nate Lawrence	Savanna Institute	nate@savannainstitute.org
Enteric Methane	Dr. Ermias Kebreab	University of California, Davis	ekebreab@ucdavis.edu
Grazing Lands	Dr. Jennifer Watts	Woodwell Climate Research Center	jwatts@woodwellclimate.org
Nutrient Management	Dr. Justin Baker	North Carolina State University	jsbaker4@ncsu.edu
Manure Management	Dr. Rebecca Larson	University of Wisconsin-Madison	rebecca.larson@wisc.edu
Soil Carbon	Dr. Bruno Basso	Michigan State University	basso@msu.edu

TECHNICAL WORK GROUP MEMBERS

Dr. Aakash Ahamed, Working Trees Inc. and Cal Poly San Luis Obispo

Dr. Ashley Conway-Anderson, University of Missouri, Center for Agroforestry

Dr. Kris Covey, Skidmore College and The Soil Inventory Project

Dr. Lingxi Chenyang, University of Utah

Dr. Nate Lawrence, Savanna Institute, Working Group Chair

Dr. Siddarth Machado, The Nature Conservancy

Dr. Chloe Wardropper, University of Illinois

RESEARCH ASSISTANCE

Dr. Emily Stutzman, Caney Fork Farms, Skidmore College

Charlie Mize, Mizelia, LLC

MERIDIAN INSTITUTE TEAM

Tori Anderson, Mediator and Program Associate, Agroforestry Technical Working Group Lead

Clare Burke Ravizza, Project Associate and Ruckelshaus Fellow

Sarah Beck, Project Associate and Ruckelshaus Fellow

Citation: Lawrence, Nate, Aakash Ahamed, Ashley Conway-Anderson, Kris Covey, Lingxi Chenyang, Siddarth Machado, Chloe Wardropper, Emily Stutzman, and Charlie Mize. "Agroforestry and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review and Technical Guidance." Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agricultural Practices, June 30, 2025. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15776654.

DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15776654

Disclaimer: The views and opinions expressed in this report are those of the listed authors and do not necessarily reflect the views or positions of all participants in the Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agriculture Practices.

Table of Contents

AGROFORESTRY AND CLIMATE OUTCOMES: LITERATURE REVIEW AND TECHNICAL GUIDANCE.....	0
ABOUT THE TECHNICAL ADVISORY NETWORK FOR CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES	1
1. PRINCIPLES FOR GHG MITIGATION IN TREE PLANTINGS	5
1.1 SYSTEM BOUNDARIES	5
1.2 AGROFORESTRY SYSTEM DESIGN PRINCIPLES FOR CLIMATE MITIGATION: AN INTEGRATED APPROACH	6
1.3 ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS DEPENDENT ON LAND MANAGER OBJECTIVES	12
1.4 PRACTICE STANDARD SPECIFIC CONSIDERATIONS	16
1.5 MEASUREMENT AND PREDICTIONS OF MITIGATION POTENTIAL	25
1.6 CONCLUSION	26
2. WORKS CITED	29
3. APPENDIX A: LITERATURE REVIEW SEARCH TERMS AND QUESTIONS	43
LITERATURE REVIEW SEARCH TERMS AND QUESTIONS.....	43
4. APPENDIX B: SCIENCE RECOMMENDATIONS.....	45
CRITICAL RESEARCH GAPS	45
GHG QUANTIFICATION	45
MEASUREMENT, DATA COLLECTION, AND DATA ACCESS.....	45
MODELING	46
OVERARCHING AGROFORESTRY SCIENCE RECOMMENDATIONS AND IMPLEMENTATION TIMELINE	46
5. APPENDIX C: KEY FINDINGS	47
KEY SCIENCE FINDINGS	47
KEY TECHNICAL RECOMMENDATIONS.....	48

1. Principles for GHG Mitigation in Tree Plantings

Agroforestry—the intentional integration of trees and shrubs into crop and livestock production systems—offers landowners a powerful tool for addressing environmental and economic challenges. Agroforestry systems can enhance productivity, protect natural resources, and increase resilience to a changing environment. In the United States, agroforestry typically includes the practices of alley cropping, forest farming, riparian buffers, silvopasture, and windbreaks. We also reviewed hedgerow plantings and tree and shrub establishment since these practices may be included in agroforestry settings. These practices have technical specifications developed by the US Department of Agriculture’s Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS), which makes cost-share funding available to landowners who implement them. This report synthesizes research on benefits and best practices associated with agroforestry practices, targeted at staff of conservation organizations advising landowners.

1.1 SYSTEM BOUNDARIES

This technical guidance document establishes system boundaries to cover direct **on-farm impacts** of agroforestry practices, including:

- Aboveground biomass accumulation and carbon storage
- Belowground carbon dynamics, including root biomass and soil organic matter
- System-level greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (e.g., soil nitrous oxide emissions, methane that is impacted by agroforestry adoption, and biomass burning)
- Resilience and stability of agroforestry systems, particularly their ability to recover from disturbance

This guidance excludes detailed quantification of **off-farm impacts**, such as:

- Lifecycle emissions from material production (e.g., planting materials, herbicides)
- Emissions from adjacent systems that are not impacted by agroforestry (e.g. enteric methane emissions that do not change from agroforestry adoption)
- Carbon substitution benefits (e.g., wood products replacing steel)
- Indirect land use changes (e.g., leakage)
- Transportation and processing emissions

While such off-farm effects require holistic consideration, they are not quantified within this primary analysis.

1.2 AGROFORESTRY SYSTEM DESIGN PRINCIPLES FOR CLIMATE MITIGATION: AN INTEGRATED APPROACH

This section provides guidance on implementing agroforestry practices to maximize climate mitigation outcomes, following the decision-making timeline that land managers typically experience. We explore tree species selection considerations, design principles, implementation approaches, and management strategies that enhance carbon sequestration and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Throughout, we focus primarily on direct, in-field impacts while providing context for post-harvest mitigation outcomes. Rather than prescribing specific species, which vary by region, this framework offers principles that can be adapted to diverse geographic contexts and landowner objectives.

1.2.1 TREE SPECIES SELECTION

Tree species characteristics significantly influence carbon sequestration and storage potential in agroforestry systems. Aboveground carbon accrual is strongly linked to increase in wood mass, with tall and large-statured trees sequestering significantly more carbon compared to small trees and shrubs. Fast-growing pioneer tree species may sequester carbon more quickly but typically have less dense wood, shorter lifespans, and decreased carbon retention compared to slow-growing tree species (Körner, 2017). Long-lived slow-growing species often have denser wood and thus hold more carbon per unit volume of wood for the longest duration of time. Denser wooded species also have stronger structural support, making them more resilient to extreme wind contributing to durable carbon accrual (Chave et al., 2009).

Root system characteristics also significantly influence carbon dynamics. Belowground carbon represents 20-40% of forest carbon pools (Bracho et al., 2023). Tree species vary in their belowground carbon allocation. Some conifer species exhibit high root-to-shoot ratios of approximately 0.54 (Samuelson et al., 2017), while certain hardwood species demonstrate ratios of 0.51-0.57 in orchard settings (Thomas et al., 2020). Fast-growing species under high resource conditions often allocate proportionally less carbon belowground, with some commercial timber species reducing belowground allocation to 10-20% of total biomass when fertilized (Retzlaff et al., 2001).

Mycorrhizal associations significantly influence both above and belowground carbon dynamics. Plant species that have associations with ectomycorrhizae in their roots show slower litter decomposition rates compared to species with arbuscular mycorrhizal associations (Choreño-Parra and Treseder, 2024). Leaf litter from ectomycorrhizal (ECM) tree species typically experience reduced decomposition rates, while arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) species often show faster organic matter turnover (Eagar et al., 2024). Consequently, ECM-associated tree species may provide superior belowground carbon benefits. Fallen deadwood and litter also contribute to above ground carbon, with woody debris from gymnosperms (typically needle-leaved) decomposing slower and retaining organic carbon longer than angiosperms (typically broadleaf; Weedon et al., 2008).

Root morphology—particularly diameter, tissue density, and depth distribution—strongly affects carbon accrual. Ma et al. (2021) demonstrated that root allocation varies systematically with climate, with higher root allocation occurring in cold and dry ecosystems. Deep-rooted species contribute carbon to deeper soil layers where stabilization mechanisms often lead to longer residence times (Pirtel et al.,

2021). Burns and Honkala (1990) provide documentation of rooting characteristics for approximately 200 North American tree species.

In addition to potential emissions, tree plantings can also impact global temperatures by changing albedo—the fraction of light reflected by the earth's surface. Recent research suggests that in certain, open, dryland ecosystems, the warming effect from reduced albedo (increased absorbance) may partially offset or, in some cases, exceed the cooling benefit from carbon sequestration (Hasler et al., 2024). In Ontario, forests dominated by evergreen, coniferous species had much lower albedo (greater absorbance and warming) than mixed or deciduous dominated forest stands (Halim et al., 2019). When planning climate-focused plantings, practitioners should consider both geographic context and species composition. Climate benefits can be optimized by carefully evaluating afforestation efforts in dryland and tundra regions, where albedo effects are strongest, and by preferentially including deciduous species in tree plantings to maintain higher surface reflectivity while capturing carbon.

1.2.2 DESIGN PRINCIPLES FOR ENHANCED CARBON SEQUESTRATION

SPECIES DIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONAL COMPOSITION

Studies indicate that diverse agroforestry systems accrue biomass and store carbon more effectively than monocultures (Ma et al., 2020; Del Rio et al., 2016). Mixed-species stands demonstrate increased productivity compared to monocultures due to niche complementarity and facilitative interactions among different species. Diverse plantings improve resource partitioning by making efficient use of vertical and horizontal stratification, reduce interspecific competition, and enhance resilience to disturbances (Del Rio et al., 2016; Turnbull et al., 2016). Species-richness may be less important than functional diversity in driving carbon benefits. Chen et al. (2024) suggest that functional diversity (leaf nutrient density, specific leaf area, wood density, and maximum tree height) may be the primary driver of this pattern, and the response to species richness may saturate. A study of forests in the USA found no productivity benefit from forests with greater than 10 species (Zeller et al., 2018). The spatial arrangement of species affects productivity and carbon outcomes. Tree-wise mixtures, where individual trees of different species are closely intermingled, typically yield higher productivity than segregated arrangements (Pretzsch et al., 2017), demonstrating how intimate spatial arrangements promote beneficial interactions and reduce competitive pressures. While mixed-species plantings can promote higher and more durable carbon accrual, very diverse systems may lead to complex management plans that can negatively affect the adoption of these practices. Practitioners should balance diversity benefits with management complexity when designing agroforestry systems.

PLANTING DENSITY AND SPACING CONSIDERATIONS

Planting density fundamentally influences both individual tree growth and system-level carbon dynamics. Trees demonstrate non-linear, density-dependent responses regarding biomass accumulation and carbon sequestration. While competition can initially boost productivity by optimizing resource use, excessive density ultimately hinders growth due to resource limitation, increased negative plant-soil feedback, and shading effects (Lekberg et al., 2018; Long and Vacchiano, 2014).

Research indicates that intermediate, optimized densities can maximize above-ground biomass accumulation, carbon sequestration, and ecosystem stability across agroforestry systems. Higher initial densities can accelerate canopy closure and early carbon sequestration, while also providing flexibility for later thinning to optimize long-term growth.

Optimal density varies significantly by agroforestry practice and system objectives. Silvopasture systems require sufficient spacing to permit forage production, with research indicating that moderate tree densities of 100-400 trees per hectare often represent an optimal balance between carbon storage and understory productivity (Jose et al., 2019). Alley cropping designs must balance tree density with crop production objectives, often leading to wider spacing between tree rows. Edge of field plantings like riparian buffers and windbreaks may feature densities greater than 1000 trees per hectare (Tufecioglu et al., 2003, Zhou et al., 2014).

Tree spacing patterns also influence system productivity and carbon outcomes. Regular spacing typically maximizes individual tree growth by providing consistent growing space, while clustered arrangements can enhance diversity of habitat and microclimate conditions. For maximum system-level carbon storage, designs should consider both horizontal and vertical space utilization, incorporating multiple canopy layers where appropriate. Species with complementary functional traits (varying canopy shapes, rooting depths, and growth forms) may allow for higher planting densities or alternative spacing arrangements by reducing direct competition for the same resources.

Image 1. Tree planting density and spacing in a pine silvopasture can affect several factors, including woody biomass accumulation, forage yield, pine straw deposition, and the practicality of management activities such as haying, logging, and pine straw deposition.

INTERACTIONS WITH ADJACENT LAND USES

Agroforestry systems create transitional zones between different land uses, with important implications for both carbon dynamics and ecological interactions. When designing agroforestry systems, careful

consideration of how agroforestry is integrated into adjacent land uses is essential for long-term success and carbon permanence.

The positioning of tree plantings relative to existing ecosystems requires particular attention. Planting trees adjacent to intact grasslands, non-forested wetlands, or other open habitats may disrupt native wildlife populations and ecological processes that depend on these non-forested environments. Thoughtful design should account for these ecological contexts to avoid unintended consequences that might lead to future tree removal.

Edge orientation affects microclimate conditions that impact both tree growth and interactions with adjacent land uses. North-south oriented edges typically receive more balanced solar radiation, while east-west edges create more pronounced shade gradients that may extend further into adjacent fields. Strategic orientation relative to prevailing winds and sun angles can optimize both protection functions and minimize competition effects.

Compatibility with adjacent land management is critical for long-term retention of agroforestry plantings. Design considerations may include appropriate spacing for equipment access, selecting tree species that minimize negative interactions (such as allelopathy or excessive shading), and adapting management practices to reduce conflicts with adjacent land uses. In some cases, edge-of-field plantings may offer carbon storage with fewer operational conflicts (Winford & Gaither, 2012; Burger, 2009). These plantings may provide various context-dependent benefits such as moderating microclimate conditions, supporting beneficial insects, or reducing erosion, while their relatively limited footprint can minimize production trade-offs (Osorio, 2019; Brandle, 1992; Knapp et al., 2023).

1.2.3 IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGIES TO MINIMIZE ESTABLISHMENT EMISSIONS

ESTABLISHING NEW TREE PLANTINGS

The establishment phase represents an initial carbon investment that must be recovered through subsequent growth and carbon sequestration. Different establishment methods carry varying carbon footprints that should be considered when designing carbon-focused systems.

Site preparation methods substantially influence immediate carbon impacts. Burger (2009) emphasizes that intensive tillage can accelerate organic matter decomposition, potentially leading to net carbon losses during establishment. When transitioning from conventional agriculture to agroforestry systems, research shows that initial soil organic carbon losses commonly occur but typically recover and increase after 4-5 years (Deng et al., 2014; Steinbeiss et al., 2008; Gamble et al., 2020).

Minimizing soil disturbance during establishment helps protect existing carbon stocks. Reduced tillage approaches, spot preparation rather than whole-field cultivation, and maintaining existing vegetation between planting rows can all help minimize initial carbon losses. For alley cropping systems, Gamble et al. (2020) found that disturbance intensity had greater impacts on soil carbon dynamics than tree species selection, highlighting the importance of low-impact installation methods.

Successful establishment is fundamental to long-term carbon outcomes. Juvenile tree success correlates with protection against herbivory (Sweeney et al., 2007), effective weed control through mulching, weed mats, or targeted herbicide application (Davies, 1985; Greenley and Rakow, 1995), appropriate irrigation in water-limited environments (Samuelson et al., 2008), and strategic nutrient management

(Retzlaff et al., 2001). Each of these establishment activities carries its own greenhouse gas footprint, but practices that increase early survival rates typically benefit long-term carbon removal. For instance, tree protection using tubes or fencing may involve embodied emissions in materials but can dramatically improve survival rates, as demonstrated in Pennsylvania where tree tubes increased survival by up to five-fold over unprotected seedlings (Sweeney et al., 2007).

*Image 2. Young chestnut trees are protected from herbivory by tree tubes grounded with stakes in a silvopasture in New York.
Photo: Emily Stutzman*

Competition control is particularly crucial for successful establishment. Davis and Trettin (2006) observed that hardwood plantations experiencing heavy weed competition showed significantly limited early growth and biomass accumulation. Their study demonstrated that adequate weed control during establishment dramatically improved growth rates and carbon sequestration potential.

Matching species to site conditions fundamentally determines establishment success and early carbon capture rates. Trugman and Anderegg (2025) emphasized that planting species poorly matched to local climate and soil leads to slowed growth, increased stress, and potentially high mortality, undermining carbon goals. Regular monitoring during establishment allows timely intervention when problems arise.

CONVERTING EXISTING FORESTS TO AGROFORESTRY SYSTEMS

Converting existing forests to agroforestry systems, most notably silvopasture or forest farming, through thinning represents an alternative implementation approach with distinct carbon implications. While this approach reduces immediate aboveground carbon stocks through tree removal, it potentially maintains much of the existing carbon, may favor increased growth that compensates initial losses, and may create productive agroforestry systems with shorter establishment timeframes. However, it's important to note that most research on thinning outcomes comes from forestry rather than

agroforestry contexts, and results may differ when forests are converted to systems with different management objectives and disturbance regimes.

The carbon implications of forest conversion likely vary with thinning intensity and approach. In forestry settings, Schaedel et al. (2017) found that precommercial thinning primarily redistributed carbon stocks among different pools (live overstory, live understory/mid-story, woody detritus, and forest floor) without significantly changing total carbon. However, excessive thinning may compromise carbon benefits, with Yang et al. (2022) recommending less than 60% thinning intensity to increase tree productivity while maintaining soil organic carbon. In hardwood forests, removing smaller-diameter trees (thinning from below) resulted in higher merchantable volume production and carbon sequestration rates compared to removing mid-sized trees or larger trees (Hoover and Stout, 2007). Whether thinning will have similar impacts in agroforestry settings remains a topic in need of greater study.

The extent of thinning varies by intended agroforestry practice. Silvopasture typically requires more intensive thinning to allow adequate light for forage development, which may reduce the likelihood of achieving the carbon benefits observed in less intensive forestry thinning. Forest farming often permits higher tree retention, potentially preserving more of the original carbon stocks. Regardless of practice, implementation should minimize initial carbon losses, properly manage woody debris to avoid emissions, promptly establish understory components, and protect soil integrity by minimizing disturbance. These principles support system establishment while attempting to balance carbon considerations with other agroforestry objectives.

1.2.4 MANAGEMENT AND MAINTENANCE FOR LONG-TERM MITIGATION

WOODY RESIDUE MANAGEMENT

The management of woody residues from pruning, thinning, and other operations significantly impacts the greenhouse gas balance of agroforestry systems. Proper residue handling can minimize emissions while potentially enhancing soil carbon sequestration.

Different disposal methods for woody debris carry varying emission profiles. Burning residues results in immediate CO₂ emissions along with potential production of methane, nitrous oxide, and particulate matter. In contrast, retaining woody debris onsite through mulching or controlled decomposition releases carbon more gradually while contributing to soil organic matter formation. Kroll et al. (2020) emphasized that retaining woody debris supports soil microbial communities and enhances soil organic matter development, particularly when incorporated into the soil profile.

In orchard settings which may have relevance in agroforestry systems, research has demonstrated that chipping non-productive trees and spreading the chips within the orchard can result in greater soil organic carbon sequestration compared to burning. Jahanzad et al. (2020) found that this practice not only reduced direct emissions but also improved soil moisture retention and reduced water stress in subsequent tree plantings. For management operations that generate smaller woody residues, such as pruning, incorporating this material into the soil through mulching or composting generally offers superior carbon outcomes compared to removal or burning.

FERTILIZATION AND INPUTS

Nutrient management in agroforestry systems influences greenhouse gas emissions, particularly through soil nitrous oxide production. While nutrition is important for tree establishment and growth, fertilization practices can affect the emission profile of the system.

Nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from fertilized soils are a concern due to this gas's high global warming potential. A global analysis of N₂O emissions in fertilized tree crops found that soil emissions increased with greater nitrogen input (Gu et al., 2019). The source of nitrogen input (e.g. chemical fertilizer, manure, or nitrogen fixing cover crops) may all contribute to increased nitrous oxide emissions (Davidson, 2009; Gelfand et al., 2016). Therefore, climate focused plantings should employ judicious use of nitrogen inputs regardless of source.

Fertilization practices also influence carbon allocation patterns within trees. Retzlaff et al. (2001) found that fertilization enhanced overall growth in conifer plantations but shifted carbon allocation toward aboveground biomass rather than roots. This shift may impact long-term carbon distribution within the system, potentially affecting belowground carbon inputs.

Other inputs can increase direct CO₂ emissions (from urea or liming) or emissions from on-farm energy use through irrigation or mechanical management. When planning agroforestry systems, consider management practices that increase tree establishment and growth while recognizing that ongoing or intensive inputs may compromise some of the climate benefits of these plantings.

1.3 ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS DEPENDENT ON LAND MANAGER OBJECTIVES

This section expands on additional land manager goals for incorporating trees on landscapes beyond climate mitigation, including conservation (1.3.1), livestock production (1.3.2), timber and biofuel production (1.3.3), and production of tree crops and non-timber products (1.3.4). These additional benefits or products may be compatible with the Natural Resource Concerns that the NRCS practices are designed to address, as long as the intent and integrity of the practice for climate mitigation is achieved and maintained.

1.3.1 CONSERVATION FOCUSED PLANTINGS

Image 3. Native pollinator alley at the Hudson Demonstration Farm, IL by the Savanna Institute. Photo: Siddarth Machado.

Conservation-focused plantings that do not anticipate future commercial harvest can present several opportunities to sequester GHG emissions and support ecosystem processes, services, and biodiversity (Udawatta et al., 2019). Planting native species with an emphasis on selecting species adapted to specific niches, soil, and other pertinent microhabitat characteristics creates resilient plant communities that provide habitat for native pollinators and wildlife.

Careful consideration should be given to selecting species appropriate to the focal site, particularly near in-tact grasslands, non-forested wetlands, etc. Edge-of-field plantings such as windbreaks that integrate native vegetation strata into planting design can offer more biodiversity value than conventional designs. Conservation-focused plantings on underutilized lands can create a matrix of vital refugia for native species, particularly in regions dominated by intense agricultural production (Tavares et al., 2019). Riparian buffers offer multiple co-benefits including erosion control, pollution interception, improved water quality besides supporting local biodiversity and creating wildlife corridors. Conservation focused plantings can also be integrated into alley cropping systems by establishing native pollinator alleys (see image above).

1.3.2 LIVESTOCK-FOCUSED PLANTINGS

In silvopasture systems, tree species selection can moderate livestock-focused benefits by providing shade and shelter that affects both livestock performance and forage productivity. Ideal tree species for shade have broad, dense canopies that reduce solar radiation, moderate soil temperatures, and increase soil moisture retention (Castillo et al., 2020; Bernardi et al., 2016). Evergreen species maintain year-round protection, while deep-rooted trees reduce competition with shallow-rooted forage,

enabling better ground cover and less bare soil, critical for erosion control and carbon sequestration (Jose et al., 2019). Fast-growing tree species can also provide more immediate benefit for livestock, but the longevity of these species must be balanced for long-term carbon benefits.

Animal productivity and GHG emission intensity are closely linked to forage quality and nutritional management. High-digestibility fodder with rich protein content and low lignin levels shifts the rumen microbiome to a more efficient profile, subsequently reducing enteric methane per kilogram of output (Alvarez et al., 2021). Strategic integration of such trees can improve animal performance while lowering emission intensity, but these benefits are often dependent on management of the system as much as species selection. The canopy architecture and species composition also influence livestock thermal comfort, with certain tree arrangements demonstrating significant reduction in heat stress (Pezzopane et al., 2019).

Grazing management significantly influences the carbon balance of these systems. Rotational grazing enhances pasture recovery, improves soil organic carbon (SOC) retention, and can reduce enteric methane emissions per unit of livestock output by increasing forage digestibility (Savian et al., 2018; Gamble et al., 2019). Studies show that rotational systems can lead to up to 30% lower methane emissions compared to continuous systems under similar stocking densities (Baronti et al., 2022).

Nitrous oxide emissions in silvopasture systems may be problematic where manure deposition exceeds plant uptake capacity. For grazing ruminants, this may result from the redistribution of nitrogen, as nutrients within the system but become concentrated in areas where animals congregate—around watering points, shade trees, and mineral stations (Matthews et al., 2010). Strategic placement of these features and even distribution of trees encourages more uniform manure distribution, reducing emission hotspots. For both ruminant and non-ruminant livestock fed with significant imported feed in addition to on-site foraged materials, careful attention to overall stocking density is critical. These systems can support artificially high animal concentrations that import substantial nutrients into the system, leading to systemic nutrient loading beyond what the plants can absorb (Hristov et al., 2013). Plantings of “living barns” may need to be particularly carefully evaluated for these considerations. Thoughtfully designed and properly managed silvopasture systems balance animal nutrition needs with ecosystem capacity, maintaining efficient nutrient cycles that enhance climate mitigation benefits, protect water quality, and ensure long-term productivity through sustainable nutrient management.

1.3.3 WOOD-PRODUCT MOTIVATED PLANTINGS

Wood-product motivated plantings represent a significant opportunity for both carbon sequestration and economic returns in agroforestry systems. These plantings, focused on timber, bioenergy, and other wood products, can provide long-term carbon storage while generating income through harvested materials.

The carbon stored in harvested wood products extends forest carbon sequestration beyond the standing tree phase. Product type dramatically influences carbon storage duration, with structural timber potentially storing carbon for decades or centuries, while paper products and bioenergy materials release carbon more quickly.

Rotation length significantly influences both carbon storage and product value. Samuelson et al. (2017) found that extending rotations in managed forests permits greater total carbon stocks, with older stands frequently surpassing 150 Mg C ha⁻¹. However, Bracho et al. (2023) demonstrated that even actively

managed systems with periodic thinning can maintain substantial carbon stocks while producing wood products. Partial cutting consistently demonstrates carbon advantages over clear-cutting, with Ola et al. (2024) finding that thinned forests maintained significantly higher carbon stocks than clear-cut forests. For wood-product plantings, selective harvest that removes mature trees while maintaining forest structure can optimize both carbon storage and wood production.

Growth characteristics and wood quality vary substantially among tree species. Fast-growing species rapidly accumulate biomass in the short term, with Dowell et al. (2009) demonstrating that certain hardwood clones achieved impressive biomass yields over just five years. However, slower-growing species with higher-density wood often provide superior long-term carbon benefits. Adaptive management approaches are essential as climate conditions change, with Van Mantgem et al. (2020) finding that forest thinning treatments can moderate drought responses, helping maintain tree vigor and carbon sequestration under variable climate conditions.

1.3.4 TREE CROP & NON-TIMBER FOREST PRODUCT PLANTINGS

Tree crops and non-timber forest products include edible products like fruits, nuts, maple syrup harvested from living trees. Tree crops may differ from non-tree crops in their functional traits in ways that impact carbon removal and storage—growth rate, mature size, and longevity, etc.—which are discussed above. From a climate mitigation perspective, harvest itself may have little impact on mitigation outcomes. Even in high-yielding maple syrup stands, tree growth rates and thus carbon removal were comparable to non-harvested stands (van den Berg et al., 2015) and berry and fruit production systems can remove and store carbon in woody biomass (Nemeth et al., 2017, Tozzini et al., 2015).

However, commercially grown tree crops often employ input-intensive management to improve crop yield or quality—nutrient inputs, irrigation, and pesticide application. These practices generally lead to both direct and indirect emissions. Other inputs can increase direct CO₂ emissions (from urea or liming) or emissions from on-farm energy use through irrigation or mechanical management. See section 1.2.4 above for more discussion of emissions related to inputs.

If tree crops decline in productivity with age, producers may choose to remove them to make way for new plantings. Climate mitigation outcomes can be achieved within tree crop production in agroforestry settings, but it's important to note that when trees are managed as crops, there may be additional sources of emissions to consider.

Incorporating diverse agroforestry practices into tree and shrub crop production landscapes may provide several benefits to adjacent tree crops including wind protection (windbreaks resulted in 27 and 34% increase in yields of raspberry and plum, respectively; Smith et al., 2021), native pollinator support from hedgerows (Morandin & Kremen, 2013), mitigation of nutrient loss to adjacent waters from riparian buffers (Salceda-Gonzalez et al., 2024), and timber production opportunities. Incorporating these practices may also provide long-lived and diversified carbon removal and storage integrated into tree crop production systems.

Other non-timber forest products include pine straw, mushrooms, basketry wood, medicinal herbs, flowers, or honey can also be produced within agroforestry practices. As with edible tree crops, low-input or no-input management approaches likely have minimal impact on climate mitigation outcomes. However, emissions may increase when production involves removing trees or the use of inputs. The

climate impact then relates to thinning practices and post-harvest wood fates, as discussed in the wood-motivated planting section above.

1.4 PRACTICE STANDARD SPECIFIC CONSIDERATIONS

This section expands on practice-specific design and management considerations that impact the potential of agroforestry and similar practices to address climate mitigation, as well as other Natural Resource Concerns. This includes alley cropping (1.4.1), forest farming (1.4.2), windbreak/shelterbelt establishment and renovation (1.4.3), silvopasture (1.4.4), riparian buffers (1.4.5), hedgerows (1.4.6), and tree and shrub establishment (1.4.7).

1.4.1 ALLEY CROPPING (311)

Alley cropping involves planting annual crops between rows of woody perennials (trees and shrubs).

Image 4. Japanese walnut and elderberry alleys with clover cover crops in between at the Hudson Demonstration Farm, IL by Savanna Institute. (Photo credit: Siddarth Machado)

Alley cropping performance is influenced by both above- and below-ground competition for soil moisture, light, and nutrients (Zamora et al., 2006; Reynolds et al., 2007; Jose et al., 2008). Some interactions can be facultative, whereby trees facilitate overall growth or production of crops, as observed in certain temperate hardwood-maize systems (Jose et al., 2004). More commonly, incorporating trees into annual cropping systems (maize, soybeans, cotton) can reduce crop growth due to resource competition. Nevertheless, when crop residue remains in the system, overall carbon

accumulation and SOC turnover typically increase, although the magnitude varies between temperate and tropical systems (Oelebermann et al., 2006).

Key considerations for alley cropping management include evaluating site moisture availability, selecting species combinations without known allelopathic interactions, and implementing practices that support nutrient management and water availability throughout the system.

1.4.2 FOREST FARMING (379)

Forest farming involves cultivating non-timber specialty products beneath a tree canopy.

Image 5. Non-timber specialty products like goldenseal can be cultivated beneath a tree canopy. (Photo credit: Katie Trozzo)

Forest farming can offer additional or alternative income streams to land managers while maintaining canopy cover and biodiversity through intentional management and multi-story cropping (Barbieri and Valdivia, 2010). Existing forest stands or woodlots can be managed to produce shade-tolerant, high-value non-timber forest products (NTFPs) suited to the understory microclimate (Baker and Saha, 2018). This approach to managing existing forested areas offers opportunities to prevent forest land conversion and preserve established carbon sinks while diversifying income streams (Trozzo et al., 2021).

Image 6. Examples of multi-story forest farming where trees, shrubs, log-grown mushroom structures, ferns, and medicinal herbs offer multi-enterprise, high-value non-timber forest products (NTFPs).

Management approaches for forest farming typically focus on creating appropriate light conditions and understory access for cultivation activities. The management of canopy density to create favorable light

conditions for understory crops is discussed more extensively in section 1.2, as these modifications have implications for system-level carbon dynamics. Selection of NTFPs that are either native or well-adapted to the region and microhabitat is critical for successful establishment and productivity. Long-term management requirements are typically low due to the understory benefits of favorable microclimate and accumulation of organic mulch, supporting both carbon sequestration goals and production objectives.

Image 7. Fruiting shiitake mushrooms are cultivated on inoculated logs placed in shaded areas, typically beneath a hardwood overstory in moist, temperate forests. This is an example of forest farming, demonstrating a productive strategy for utilizing forest environments and resources to cultivate food.

1.4.3 WINDBREAK/SHELTERBELT ESTABLISHMENT AND RENOVATION (380)

Windbreaks involve planting several rows of trees to shelter crops, livestock, and soil from wind. The rows can include edible species that provide additional income while supporting wildlife.

Windbreaks frequently utilize diverse, dense plantings of trees and shrubs with multiple canopy strata and inclusion of fast-growing, large, and longer-lived trees—following many of the recommendations in section 1.2. This design approach may help explain the relatively high rates of biomass carbon removal within the windbreak footprint (Possu et al., 2004). Windbreaks have also been shown to increase yields of adjacent crops and forages in protected areas (Osorio, 2019; Brandle, 1992), and may also reduce nitrous oxide emissions by enhancing crop/forage nitrogen uptake and removal compared to unprotected areas. However, nitrogen application rate remains the strongest predictor of emissions

Image 8. Trees planted in windbreaks form structural barriers between fields of annual row crops.

(Eagle et al., 2017), so increased yield alone may not reduce emissions from the protected area, and this effect has not been empirically demonstrated from windbreaks.

Image 8. Illustration of positive effects of windbreaks within the windbreaks themselves as well as on adjacent crops.

Windbreaks designed to maximize climate mitigation benefits will include multiple species and incorporate functional diversity. Planting fast-growing trees alongside slower growing or longer-lived species may reduce the frequency of windbreak restoration. When renovating a windbreak, land managers should choose options that minimize emissions (see sections above) while restoring windbreak function and addressing landowner objectives to promote windbreak retention.

1.4.4 SILVOPASTURE (381)

Silvopasture combines trees and livestock within the same field. Trees provide shade, shelter, and potentially food for grazing animals, while also serving timber, fruit, or fodder purposes.

Image 9. Combination of trees and livestock within the same field. Trees will provide shade, shelter, and food for grazing animals. The trees can also be used for timber, fruit, or fodder. (Photo credit: Alexandra Ramirez)

From a climate mitigation perspective, silvopasture presents unique considerations regarding both livestock-related emissions and carbon sequestration. Grazing management significantly influences the carbon balance of these systems. Rotational grazing enhances pasture recovery, improves soil organic

carbon (SOC) retention, and can reduce enteric methane emissions per unit of livestock output by increasing forage digestibility (Savian et al., 2018; Gamble et al., 2019). Rotational systems can lead to up to 30% lower methane emissions compared to continuous systems under similar stocking densities (Baronti et al., 2022). These benefits relate to improved forage quality, root mass, and soil structure, which contribute to better carbon cycling and lower nitrous oxide losses (O'Grady et al., 2024).

Image 10. Sheep graze in a rotational grazing system within a silvopasture setting. Temporary fencing is used to create small paddocks for intensive grazing, and the sheep are frequently moved between them. The silvopasture includes fruit- and nut-bearing trees.

The inclusion of fodder trees and shrubs within silvopasture systems for ruminants may further reduce enteric methane emissions. High-digestibility fodder with high protein content and low lignin levels can shift the rumen microbiome to a more efficient profile, subsequently reducing enteric methane per kilogram of output (Alvarez et al., 2021). Strategic integration of such fodder trees can improve animal performance while lowering emission intensity, providing an additional climate benefit beyond carbon sequestration in woody biomass. However, this effect is dependent upon several other factors, including but not limited to the species of ruminant, the remainder of their diet, the species of fodder, and seasonal growing conditions that would affect tannin content of the plants.

Incorporating diverse tree species with complementary functional traits enhances system resilience and carbon storage potential while potentially providing multiple products (timber, fruit, fodder).

When establishing silvopasture systems, practitioners have multiple approaches available, including planting trees into existing pastures or modifying existing forest stands. Each approach has different implications for initial and long-term carbon dynamics, with forest conversion considerations discussed more extensively in section 1.2.

1.4.5 RIPARIAN FOREST BUFFERS (391)

Riparian forest buffers involve planting trees along rivers, lakes, or ponds to filter runoff and decrease soil erosion while supporting wildlife.

Image 11. Planting trees along rivers, lakes, or ponds to help filter runoff and decrease soil erosion. This type of practice can also support wildlife. (Photo credit: Alexandra Ramirez)

Riparian forest buffers are ideal edge-of-field practices in appropriate biogeographies where trees and woody species are adapted to riparian habitats and form transition zones between upland and aquatic habitats. These systems accumulate woody biomass, creating above- and below-ground carbon sinks while providing habitat and structure with numerous environmental benefits (Udawatta et al., 2022; Balian and Naiman, 2005; Rheinhardt et al., 2012; Tufekcioglu et al., 2003; Matzek et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2010).

Image 12. Native species of pine, sycamore, and oaks are planted, extending the riparian buffer beyond its original range.

Riparian forests form canopies that shade and lower water temperatures, while the physical vegetation structure intercepts organic and inorganic debris from entering water flow pathways and reduces soil erosion. The interception of surface runoff reduces flow rates and promotes enhanced water infiltration, allowing riparian vegetation roots to intercept fertilizers and pollutants, which can reduce indirect nitrous oxide emissions from nitrogen runoff. The combined functions of riparian forests support healthy soil and better water quality.

However, riparian forest buffers can be sources of emissions in frequently flooded areas with anaerobic soils. Anoxic conditions within soil and submerged vegetation, including organic debris, enhance anaerobic processes that emit CO₂, methane (CH₄) (Fischer et al., 2013; Kim et al., 2010). Recent research has shown that trees growing in wetland environments can act as conduits for methane transport from anaerobic soils to the atmosphere. Covey and Megonigal (2019) demonstrated that trees can both transport soil-produced methane and potentially produce methane through several pathways. The magnitude of these emissions varies by tree species, soil conditions, and hydrologic regime. In riparian zones with seasonal flooding or consistently high water tables, methane emissions through trees may significantly reduce the overall climate mitigation benefits compared to upland plantings.

Image 13. Depiction of positive effects of riparian buffers related to soil and nutrient conservation, flood mediation, and provision of wildlife habitat.

Several strategies using catchment-based approaches can reduce emissions from riparian buffers (Cole et al., 2020). Drainage systems can be modified, and streambanks recontoured to prevent prolonged saturation and restore natural flow regimes. Spatial planning of planting efforts should incorporate species appropriateness by selecting deep-rooted native species that improve soil aeration. Buffer zone integration with adjacent land-use practices ensures the buffer is designed appropriately for surrounding conditions.

Image 14. Non-timber forest products riparian buffer.

1.4.6 HEDGEROW PLANTING (422)

Hedgerows are linear plantings of woody plant species designed to provide wildlife with cover and food while offering benefits similar to traditional windbreaks and shelterbelts.

Image 15. Hedgerows are linear plantings of woody plant species designed to provide wildlife with cover and food, while also providing the benefits of traditional windbreaks and shelterbelts.

Hedgerows have a distinct benefit as an edge-of-field agroforestry practice that is unlikely to negatively impact in-field production. When strategically designed with deep-rooted, ectomycorrhizal species, hedgerows can create extensive belowground carbon sinks through fungal networks that stabilize soil aggregates and slow decomposition processes (Refsland et al., 2023; Eagar et al., 2024). Additionally, hedgerows function as windbreaks that reduce soil erosion and moisture loss in adjacent fields, indirectly decreasing energy requirements for irrigation and tillage (Schweitzer, 2019).

Research indicates that incorporating nitrogen-fixing species within hedgerows can reduce the need for synthetic fertilizers in neighboring crops, thereby cutting nitrous oxide emissions associated with fertilizer application (Ansari, 2023). Hedgerows can also benefit operations by providing habitat for beneficial insects that enhance natural pest control, potentially reducing emissions from pesticides (Knapp et al., 2023). As a result, hedgerows represent an accessible entry point for farmers to participate in climate mitigation while simultaneously enhancing farm resilience and ecological services.

1.4.7 TREE AND SHRUB ESTABLISHMENT (612)

Successful establishment of trees and shrubs forms the foundation for long-term carbon sequestration in agroforestry systems. The early years of tree development critically influence subsequent growth trajectory, survival rates, and ultimately carbon sequestration potential.

The establishment phase represents an initial carbon investment that must be recovered through subsequent growth and carbon sequestration. Different establishment methods carry varying carbon footprints that should be considered when designing carbon-focused systems.

Matching species to site conditions fundamentally determines establishment success and early carbon capture rates. Trugman and Anderegg (2025) emphasized that planting species poorly matched to local climate and soil leads to slowed growth, increased stress, and potentially high mortality, undermining carbon goals. Incorporating functional diversity enhances system resilience and carbon sequestration potential, with Turnbull et al. (2016) demonstrating that diverse plant communities generally outperform monocultures in ecosystem functioning, including productivity and resource utilization. Invasive species pose significant risks to both establishment success and long-term carbon sequestration, with Knapp et al. (2023) finding that invasive plants can dramatically reduce native plant regeneration, potentially undermining carbon goals.

Planting density affects both individual tree growth and stand-level carbon accumulation. Ile et al. (2021) observed that in certain hardwood systems, higher density plantings generated significantly greater fine root biomass than lower density plantings. For carbon-focused establishments, higher initial densities can accelerate canopy closure and carbon sequestration. Competition control is crucial for successful establishment, with Davis and Trettin (2006) observing that hardwood plantations experiencing heavy weed competition showed significantly limited early growth and biomass accumulation. Their study demonstrated that adequate weed control during establishment dramatically improved growth rates and carbon sequestration potential.

Regular monitoring of establishment success allows timely intervention when problems arise. Early thinning or pruning decisions significantly influence carbon allocation in young stands, with Zhang et al. (2024) finding that appropriately timed thinning typically enhances carbon sequestration rates in the remaining trees. Planning for disturbance resilience during establishment fundamentally protects long-term carbon sequestration potential, with Dye et al. (2024) emphasizing that natural disturbances can rapidly convert forest carbon sinks into net sources.

1.5 MEASUREMENT AND PREDICTIONS OF MITIGATION POTENTIAL

Agroforestry practices increase woody biomass carbon stocks through the integration of trees into agricultural landscapes. While traditional field measurements have relied on allometric equations developed for forestry, new technologies like LiDAR and digital tools have improved accessibility and accuracy of carbon measurements (Demol et al., 2024; Ahamed et al., 2023).

For climate-motivated plantings, practitioners may benefit from reliable estimates of anticipated carbon benefits from specific agroforestry implementations. The USDA's COMET-Farm platform offers a tool for predicting biomass carbon accumulation in agroforestry systems. Users can select pre-defined scenarios or define their own. We evaluated the effectiveness of the custom scenarios tool by comparing model predictions against empirical measurements from published studies including 19 individual scenarios spanning diverse geographic regions, tree ages (7-48 years), and practices (alley cropping, riparian buffers, silvopasture, and windbreaks).

The average woody biomass carbon sequestration rate for all agroforestry scenarios in our review was 2.0 Mg of carbon dioxide per acre, per year. This overall average may be useful for informing the carbon potential of agroforestry across a broad range of scenarios. We found no evidence that planting practice was predictive of carbon removal (for instance, that one agroforestry practice systematically removed more carbon in biomass than another practice). Rather, carbon outcomes were dictated by a range of factors including planting site, species selection, and planting density discussed in section 1.2 above.

Our analysis suggested COMET-Farm's predictive accuracy varies by context. The model estimates were least accurate in younger plantings (under 15 years) and in high-density plantings (over 1000 trees/hectare), with some error rates exceeding 400% in these scenarios (Figure 1). Averaged across all studies, COMET overpredicted carbon by 47%, but this overestimate was largely driven by a few young and/or high-density plantings. In plantings over 15 years old and with planting densities under 400 trees/acre, COMET provided a slightly conservative average estimate (-18% of the measured value).

Under these scenarios, COMET was able to reasonably predict carbon outcomes across a large geography. Practitioners should use caution when interpreting COMET-Farm results, particularly for assessments made for short duration (young trees) or high planting densities, but COMET may otherwise provide a reasonable starting point for estimating mitigation impacts.

COMET’s predictions could potentially be improved in several ways. Firstly, Incorporation of tree competition effects at higher planting densities and low growth rate in younger trees could improve early predictions. Secondly, a more thorough investigation and parameterization of factors such as geography, climate, topography, and other geospatial variables could improve COMET predictions. Lastly, intercomparison with other modeling approaches created for a similar purpose (e.g. iTree, Forest Vegetation) could help reveal model inconsistencies, and an ensemble modeling approach could potentially benefit both the research and practitioner communities.

Figure 1. Percentage error of COMET biomass carbon estimate compared to measured values from published agroforestry studies. The grey bar denotes the zone where COMET predicted with 50% of the actual, measured value. Panel A features an X axis of planting age. Panel B features an X value of planting density.

1.6 CONCLUSION

Agroforestry offers landowners and managers a powerful tool for addressing environmental and economic challenges by intentionally integrating trees and shrubs into crop and livestock production systems. Key considerations for adopting agroforestry include their primary objective: conservation, livestock, timber, non-timber products, or climate mitigation/resilience. Decision-making support is provided to guide choices related to planting strategies, species selection, and management practices tailored to these objectives.

To maximize climate mitigation benefits across agroforestry systems, this technical guidance recommends specific implementation strategies tailored to each Conservation Practice Standard (CPS), informed by up-to-date scientific literature and empirical research. For **Alley Cropping** (CPS 311),

practitioners should prioritize species combinations that minimize competition and avoid allelopathic interactions, while carefully balancing tree density and spacing to reduce resource competition with crops (Section 1.4.1). Carbon outcomes can be enhanced by leaving crop residues in place and avoiding intensive tillage, as disturbance during establishment often results in short-term soil organic carbon (SOC) losses (Section 1.2.3).

In **Forest Farming** (CPS 379), mitigation benefits are best maintained by preserving existing canopy cover and enhancing understory productivity with native or regionally adapted non-timber forest products (NTFPs), which typically require fewer inputs and support carbon retention in both biomass and soils (Section 1.4.2). Forest farming systems should avoid heavy thinning and favor low-disturbance understory management strategies to preserve soil integrity and long-term carbon pools (Section 1.2.4).

Windbreaks and Shelterbelts (CPS 380) are most effective when designed with a mix of species that include fast-growing pioneers and long-lived, deep-rooted trees, ideally arranged in multi-strata configurations (Section 1.4.3). These plantings provide carbon storage benefits both within the tree rows and by enhancing adjacent crop productivity, though input reductions in protected areas must be carefully managed to realize full mitigation potential (Section 1.2.2). Renovation activities should minimize emissions through selective replacement strategies rather than complete clearing and replanting (Section 1.2.4).

For **Silvopasture** (CPS 381), rotational grazing is a key strategy to increase forage digestibility and SOC retention while reducing methane emissions per unit of animal output (Section 1.4.4). Integrating high-digestibility fodder trees further reduces enteric methane but must be coupled with careful species selection and nutrient management to avoid emission hotspots, especially around shade and water sources (Section 1.3.2). Converting existing forests into silvopasture systems should be done with caution; moderate thinning retains more carbon and ensures better long-term sequestration potential (Section 1.2.4).

Riparian Forest Buffers (CPS 391) provide robust carbon sinks and additional benefits like erosion control and nutrient interception when native, deep-rooted species are used (Section 1.4.5). However, in flood-prone zones with anaerobic soils, methane emissions can offset carbon gains. Design adaptations—such as species selection, drainage improvements, and spatial planning—can help mitigate these effects (Section 1.4.5; Section 1.2.2).

Hedgerow Plantings (CPS 422) serve as a low-input mitigation strategy, particularly effective when incorporating nitrogen-fixing and ectomycorrhizal species to enhance belowground carbon storage and soil aggregation (Section 1.4.6). Strategically located hedgerows also improve habitat for beneficial insects, reducing the need for pesticides and contributing to indirect emissions reductions (Section 1.3.1).

Finally, **Tree and Shrub Establishment** (CPS 612) underpins all agroforestry practices. Selecting species that are well-suited to site conditions—accounting for soil type, climate, and hydrology—is critical for survival and long-term carbon sequestration (Section 1.4.7). Higher initial planting densities can accelerate canopy closure and carbon accrual, though eventual thinning should be timed to enhance growth without sacrificing stored carbon (Section 1.2.2; Section 1.2.4). Low-disturbance establishment methods, strong competition control (e.g., mulching), and regular monitoring are key to early success and efficient carbon capture (Section 1.2.3).

Across all practices, integrating species with high biomass potential, deep root systems, and dense wood, particularly those forming ectomycorrhizal associations, offers the greatest potential for long-term carbon storage (Section 1.2.1). Functional diversity within and between species enhances productivity, resilience, and mitigation potential, but should be balanced with the complexity of management (Section 1.2.2). Minimizing inputs, especially nitrogen fertilizers and synthetic chemicals, is essential to prevent unintended GHG emissions (Section 1.2.4). Tools like COMET-Farm can support practitioners in estimating carbon outcomes but should be interpreted cautiously, particularly for young or high-density systems where prediction errors are more pronounced (Section 1.5). Ultimately, successful climate mitigation through agroforestry requires aligning system design and management with local ecological contexts and landowner goals, while maintaining a long-term perspective on carbon benefits.

There are several pressing data and research gaps that constrain the accurate estimation and optimization of climate mitigation benefits in agroforestry systems. A significant limitation is the lack of empirical greenhouse gas (GHG) measurements specifically from agroforestry contexts. Most available data on nitrous oxide and methane emissions are drawn from forestry or monoculture agricultural systems, making them poorly suited for capturing the complex interactions present in integrated tree-crop-livestock environments (Section 1.2.3). Belowground carbon dynamics—including root biomass, depth, turnover, and mycorrhizal associations—are also underrepresented in current datasets, even though they comprise 20–40% of total forest carbon pools and play a key role in long-term carbon stabilization (Section 1.2.1). Methane emissions from flooded riparian systems, particularly those mediated by tree root systems and anaerobic soil conditions, remain poorly quantified (Section 1.4.5). Furthermore, the climatic impact of biophysical factors such as changes in surface albedo is rarely integrated into mitigation assessments, despite research showing that afforestation in snow-prone or dryland regions may increase local warming (Section 1.2.1).

Modeling tools like COMET-Farm, while useful, also exhibit notable weaknesses. The report finds that COMET often overestimates carbon sequestration in younger (<15 years) and high-density (>1000 trees/ha) plantings, with error rates exceeding 400% in some scenarios (Section 1.5). There is also a lack of robust, practice-specific GHG quantification: carbon outcomes are not consistently linked to the type of conservation practice implemented (e.g., alley cropping vs. windbreaks), but rather to site-specific factors such as species traits, planting density, and local management decisions (Sections 1.2.2 and 1.5). Long-term field studies are limited, leaving gaps in understanding how maintenance actions like thinning and pruning, or disturbances such as drought and pests, affect carbon storage and permanence over time (Section 1.2.4). Finally, the impacts of nutrient loading, manure concentration, and livestock behavior in silvopasture systems are still not fully understood in terms of GHG fluxes (Section 1.3.2). Addressing these gaps is essential to improve the accuracy of carbon modeling, inform technical practice guidance, and build confidence in agroforestry as a reliable climate mitigation strategy.

2. Works Cited

Adewopo, J. B., M. L. Silveira, S. Xu, S. Gerber, L. E. Sollenberger, and T. A. Martin. 2014. "Management Intensification Impacts on Soil and Ecosystem Carbon Stocks in Subtropical Grasslands." *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 78 (3): 977–86. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2013.12.0523>.

Ahamed, Aakash, John Foye, Sanjok Poudel, Erich Trieschman, and John Fike. 2023. "Measuring Tree Diameter with Photogrammetry Using Mobile Phone Cameras." *Forests* 14 (10): 2027. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14102027>.

Alberti, G., S. Vicca, I. Inglima, L. Belelli-Marchesini, L. Genesio, F. Miglietta, H. Marjanovic, et al. 2015. "Soil C:N Stoichiometry Controls Carbon Sink Partitioning between above-Ground Tree Biomass and Soil Organic Matter in High Fertility Forests." *IFOREST-BIOGEOSCIENCES AND FORESTRY* 8 (April): 195–206. <https://doi.org/10.3832/ifor1196-008>.

Álvarez, F., F. Casanoves, J. C. Suárez, and D. Pezo. 2021. "The Effect of Different Levels of Tree Cover on Milk Production in Dual-Purpose Livestock Systems in the Humid Tropics of the Colombian Amazon Region." *Agroforestry Systems* 95 (6): 1125–1137. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-020-00566-7>.

Ansari, J., R. P. Udawatta, and S. H. Anderson. 2023. "Soil Nitrous Oxide Emission from Agroforestry, Rowcrop, Grassland and Forests in North America: A Review." *Agroforestry Systems* 97 (8): 1465–1479. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-023-00870-y>.

Ares, Adrian, and David Brauer. 2005. "Aboveground Biomass Partitioning in Loblolly Pine Silvopastoral Stands: Spatial Configuration and Pruning Effects." *Forest Ecology and Management* 219 (2): 176–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2005.08.042>.

Aspinwall, M. J., J. S. King, S. E. McKeand, and B. P. Bullock. 2011. "Genetic Effects on Stand-Level Uniformity and above- and Belowground Dry Mass Production in Juvenile Loblolly Pine." *FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT* 262 (4): 609–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2011.04.029>.

Baker, S. A., and S. Saha. 2018. "Forest Farming in Georgia's Piedmont and Coastal Plain: A Survey of Land Management Practices, Potential, and Perspectives." *Agricultural Science* 9 (4): 421–433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aasci.2018.04.003>.

Balian, E. V., and R. J. Naiman. 2005. "Abundance and Production of Riparian Trees in the Lowland Floodplain of the Queets River, Washington." *Ecosystems* 8 (7): 841–861. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-005-0043-4>.

Barbieri, C., and C. Valdivia. 2010. "Recreation and Agroforestry: Examining New Dimensions of Multifunctionality in Family Farms." *Journal of Rural Studies* 26 (4): 465–473. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-009-9269-z>.

Baronti, S., F. Ungaro, A. Maienza, and F. Ugolini. 2022. "Rotational Pasture Management to Increase the Sustainability of Mountain Livestock Farms in the Alpine Region." *Regional Environmental Change* 22: 128. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-022-01896-1>.

- Bazrgar, Amir Behzad, Naresh Thevathasan, Andrew Gordon, and Jamie Simpson. 2024. "Allometric Equations for Estimating Aboveground Biomass Carbon in Five Tree Species Grown in an Intercropping Agroforestry System in Southern Ontario, Canada." *Agroforestry Systems* 98 (3): 739–49. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-023-00942-z>.
- Berg, Abby K. van den, Timothy D. Perkins, Mark L. Isselhardt, and Timothy R. Wilmot. 2016. "Growth Rates of Sugar Maple Trees Tapped for Maple Syrup Production Using High-Yield Sap Collection Practices." *Forest Science* 62 (1): 107–14. <https://doi.org/10.5849/forsci.15-019>.
- Bernardi, R. E., I. K. de Jonge, and M. Holmgren. 2016. "Trees Improve Forage Quality and Abundance in South American Subtropical Grasslands." *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 233: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.08.002>.
- Berryman, E., M. G. Ryan, J. B. Bradford, T. J. Hawbaker, and R. Birdsey. 2016. "Total Belowground Carbon Flux in Subalpine Forests Is Related to Leaf Area Index, Soil Nitrogen, and Tree Height." *ECOSPHERE* 7 (8). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.1418>.
- Bracho, R., T. A. Martin, J. G. Vogel, W. P. Cropper Jr., G. Celis, K. Clark, H. L. Gholz, et al. 2023. "Two Decades of Carbon Dynamics in an Actively-Managed, Naturally-Regenerated Longleaf/Slash Pine Forest." *Forest Ecology and Management* 548 (November). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2023.121408>.
- Bragg, D. C. 2012. "Developing Contemporary and Historical Live Tree Biomass Estimates for Old Pine-Hardwood Stands of the Midsouth, USA." *FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT* 281 (October): 32–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2012.06.015>.
- Brandle, J. R., B. B. Johnson, and T. Akeson. 1992. "Field Windbreaks: Are They Economical?" *Journal of Production Agriculture* 5 (3): 393–398. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jpa1992.0393>.
- Burger, J. A. 2009. "Management Effects on Growth, Production and Sustainability of Managed Forest Ecosystems: Past Trends and Future Directions." *Forest Ecology and Management* 258 (10): 2335–2346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2009.03.015>.
- Burns, Russell M., and Barbara H. Honkala, tech. coords. 1990. *Silvics of North America: 1. Conifers; 2. Hardwoods*. Agriculture Handbook 654. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service. https://www.srs.fs.usda.gov/pubs/misc/ag_654/table_of_contents.htm.
- Butnor, J. R., L. J. Samuelson, T. A. Stokes, K. H. Johnsen, P. H. Anderson, and C. A. González-Benecke. 2016. "Surface-Based GPR Underestimates below-Stump Root Biomass." *PLANT AND SOIL* 402 (1–2): 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-015-2768-y>.
- Castillo, M. S., F. Tiezzi, and A. J. Franzluebbers. 2020. "Tree Species Effects on Understory Forage Productivity and Microclimate in a Silvopasture of the Southeastern USA." *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 296: 106932. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106932>.
- Chatterjee, A., G. F. Vance, and D. B. Tinker. 2009. "Carbon Pools of Managed and Unmanaged Stands of Ponderosa and Lodgepole Pine Forests in Wyoming." *CANADIAN JOURNAL OF FOREST RESEARCH* 39 (10): 1893–1900. <https://doi.org/10.1139/X09-112>.

Chave, J., D. Coomes, S. Jansen, S. L. Lewis, N. G. Swenson, and A. E. Zanne. 2009. "Towards a Worldwide Wood Economics Spectrum." *Ecology Letters* 12 (4): 351–366. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01285.x>.

Chen, C., Y. Zheng, S. C. Thomas, and R. Waller. 2024. "Resource Availability Enhances Positive Tree Functional Diversity Effects on Carbon and Nitrogen Accrual in Natural Forests." *Nature Communications* 15: 1138. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-53004-y>.

Chen, W. L., R. T. Koide, T. S. Adams, J. L. DeForest, L. Cheng, and D. M. Eissenstat. 2016. "Root Morphology and Mycorrhizal Symbioses Together Shape Nutrient Foraging Strategies of Temperate Trees." *PROCEEDINGS OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA* 113 (31): 8741–46. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1601006113>.

Chojnacky, D. C., L. S. Heath, and J. C. Jenkins. 2014. "Updated Generalized Biomass Equations for North American Tree Species." *FORESTRY* 87 (1): 129–51. <https://doi.org/10.1093/forestry/cpt053>.

Choreño-Parra, J. A., and K. K. Treseder. 2024. "Mycorrhizal Networks Interact with Rhizodeposition to Mediate Soil Carbon Cycling." *New Phytologist* 241 (3): 1072–1091. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.19748>.

Cole, L. J., D. Kleijn, L. V. Dicks, J. C. Stout, S. G. Potts, M. Albrecht, M. V. Balzan, et al. 2020. "A Critical Analysis of the Potential for EU Common Agricultural Policy Measures to Support Wild Pollinators on Farmland." *Journal of Applied Ecology* 57 (4): 681–694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106891>.

Covey, Kristofer R., and J. Patrick Megonigal. 2019. "Methane Production and Emissions in Trees and Forests." *New Phytologist* 222 (1): 35–51. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.15624>.

Davidson, E. A. 2009. "The Contribution of Manure and Fertilizer Nitrogen to Atmospheric Nitrous Oxide Since 1860." *Nature Geoscience* 2 (9): 659–662. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo608>.

Davies, R. J. 1985. "The Importance of Weed Control and the Use of Tree Shelters for Establishing Broadleaved Trees on Grass-Dominated Sites in England." *Forestry* 58 (2): 167–80. <https://doi.org/10.1093/forestry/58.2.167>.

Davis, A. A., and C. C. Trettin. 2006. "Sycamore and Sweetgum Plantation Productivity on Former Agricultural Land in South Carolina." *Biomass & Bioenergy* 30 (8–9): 769–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2005.08.001>.

Del Rio, M., H. Pretzsch, R. Ruiz-Peinado, E. Ampoorter, P. Annighöfer, I. Barbeito, I. Bielak, et al. 2016. "Species Interactions Increase the Temporal Stability of Community Productivity in *Pinus Sylvestris*–*Fagus Sylvatica* Mixtures across Europe." *Journal of Ecology* 104 (2): 306–317. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.12727>.

Demol, Miro, Kechang Yin, Ji Qi, Bingyang Cui, Sruthi M. Krishna Moorthy, and Hans Verbeeck. 2024. "Above-Ground Biomass Mapping in a Tropical Mountain Forest by Integrating Multiple Data Sources with a 3D Forest Model." *Communications Earth & Environment* 5 (1): 31. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01448-x>.

Deng, L., G. Bin Liu, and Z. P. Shangguan. 2014. "Land-Use Conversion and Changing Soil Carbon Stocks in China's 'Grain-for-Green' Program: A Synthesis." *Global Change Biology* 20 (11): 3544–3556. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12508>.

Dewalle, David R., and Gordon M. Heisler. 1988. "Use of Windbreaks for Home Energy Conservation." *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 22–23: 243–60. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8809\(88\)90024-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8809(88)90024-2).

Disney, M. I., M. Burt, K. Calders, C. Schaaf, and A. Stovall. 2020. "Innovations in Ground and Airborne Technologies as Reference and for Training and Validation: Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS)." *Surveys in Geophysics* 41 (1): 29–61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-019-09527-x>.

Dold, C., Andrew L. Thomas, A. J. Ashworth, D. Philipp, D. K. Brauer, and T. J. Sauer. 2019. "Carbon Sequestration and Nitrogen Uptake in a Temperate Silvopasture System." *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* 114 (1): 85–98. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-019-09987-y>.

Dowell, R. C., D. Gibbins, J. L. Rhoads, and S. G. Pallardy. 2009. "Biomass Production Physiology and Soil Carbon Dynamics in Short-Rotation-Grown *Populus Deltoides* and *P. Deltoides* x *P. Nigra* Hybrids." *Forest Ecology and Management* 257 (1): 134–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2008.08.023>.

Dye, A. W., R. M. Houtman, P. Gao, W. R. L. Anderegg, C. J. Fettig, J. A. Hicke, J. B. Kim, et al. 2024. "Carbon, Climate, and Natural Disturbance: A Review of Mechanisms, Challenges, and Tools for Understanding Forest Carbon Stability in an Uncertain Future." *Carbon Balance and Management* 19 (1): 35. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13021-024-00282-0>.

Eagle, Alison J., Lydia P. Olander, Katie L. Locklier, James B. Heffernan, and Emily S. Bernhardt. 2017. "Fertilizer Management and Environmental Factors Drive N₂O and NO₃ Losses in Corn: A Meta-Analysis." *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 81 (5): 1191–1202. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2016.09.0281>.

Eagar, A., J. A. Bennett, and J. Karst. 2024. "Plant-Soil Feedback Mechanisms with Implications for Forest Management." *Journal of Ecology* 112 (1): 214–231.

Fischer, J., L. Fortmann, C. Geertz, D. Ghimire, M. Goldman, C. Harris, J. Herrera, et al. 2013. "Emissions from Drained Organic Agricultural Soils." In *2013 Supplement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories: Wetlands*, edited by T. Hiraishi, T. Krug, K. Tanabe, N. Srivastava, J. Baasansuren, M. Fukuda, and T. G. Troxler, 2.1–2.79. Geneva: IPCC.

Fitch, A. A., S. B. Goldsmith, R. A. Lankau, N. Wurzbarger, Z. D. Shortt, A. Vratatos, E. N. Laurent, and C. E. H. Pries. 2024. "Mycorrhizal Associations of Temperate Forest Seedlings Mediate Rhizodeposition, but Not Soil Carbon Storage, under Elevated Nitrogen Availability." *GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY* 30 (8). <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17446>.

Forfora, N., I. Azuaje, K. A. Vivas, R. E. Vera, A. Brito, R. Venditti, S. Kelley, Q. S. Tu, A. Woodley, and R. Gonzalez. 2024. "Evaluating Biomass Sustainability: Why below-Ground Carbon Sequestration Matters." *JOURNAL OF CLEANER PRODUCTION* 439 (February). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.140677>.

Gamble, J. D., G. A. Johnson, D. A. Current, D. L. Wyse, D. S. Zamora, and C. C. Sheaffer. 2020. "Alley Cropping Affects Perennial Bioenergy Crop Root Distribution, Carbon, and Nutrient Stocks." *Agronomy Journal* 112 (5): 3718–32. <https://doi.org/10.1002/agj2.20350>.

Gay, J. D., B. Currey, K. T. Davis, and E. N. J. Brookshire. 2024. "Functional Attributes of Conifers Expanding into Temperate Semi-Arid Grasslands Modulate Carbon and Nitrogen Fluxes in Response to Prescribed Fire." *BIOGEOCHEMISTRY* 167 (11): 1335–52. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-024-01168-6>.

Gelfand, I., I. Shcherbak, N. Millar, A. N. Kravchenko, and G. P. Robertson. 2016. "Long-Term Nitrous Oxide Fluxes in Annual and Perennial Agricultural and Unmanaged Ecosystems in the Upper Midwest USA." *Global Change Biology* 22 (11): 3594–3607. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13426>.

Goebel, M., S. E. Hobbie, B. Bulaj, M. Zadworny, D. D. Archibald, J. Oleksyn, P. B. Reich, and D. M. Eissenstat. 2011. "Decomposition of the Finest Root Branching Orders: Linking Belowground Dynamics to Fine-Root Function and Structure." *ECOLOGICAL MONOGRAPHS* 81 (1): 89–102. <https://doi.org/10.1890/09-2390.1>.

Gonzalez-Benecke, C. A., S. A. Gezan, T. J. Albaugh, H. L. Allen, H. E. Burkhart, T. R. Fox, E. J. Jokela, et al. 2014. "Local and General Above-Stump Biomass Functions for Loblolly Pine and Slash Pine Trees." *FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT* 334 (December): 254–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2014.09.002>.

GOWER, S. T., K. A. VOGT, and C. C. GRIER. 1992. "CARBON DYNAMICS OF ROCKY-MOUNTAIN DOUGLAS-FIR - INFLUENCE OF WATER AND NUTRIENT AVAILABILITY." *ECOLOGICAL MONOGRAPHS* 62 (1): 43–65. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2937170>.

Greenley, Katrina M., and Donald A. Rakow. 1995. "The Effect of Wood Mulch Type and Depth on Weed and Tree Growth and Certain Soil Parameters." *Arboriculture & Urban Forestry* 21 (5): 225–32. <https://doi.org/10.48044/jauf.1995.036>.

Gu, Jiangxin, Huanghua Nie, Haojie Guo, Huanhuan Xu, and Tongdee Gunnathorn. 2019. "Nitrous Oxide Emissions from Fruit Orchards: A Review." *Atmospheric Environment* 201 (March): 166–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.12.046>.

Halim, Mohammad Abdul, Han Y. H. Chen, and Sean C. Thomas. 2019. "Stand Age and Species Composition Effects on Surface Albedo in a Mixedwood Boreal Forest." *Biogeosciences* 16 (22): 4357–75. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-16-4357-2019>.

Hasler, Natalia, Christopher A. Williams, Vanessa Carrasco Denney, Peter W. Ellis, Surendra Shrestha, Drew E. Terasaki Hart, Nicholas H. Wolff, et al. 2024. "Accounting for Albedo Change to Identify Climate-Positive Tree Cover Restoration." *Nature Communications* 15 (1): 2275. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-46577-1>.

Holcomb, D., M. Castle, and G. Shriver. 2023. "CoastalTree: A Smartphone Application to Map Coastal Forests and Trees." *Remote Sensing* 15 (3): 772. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15030772>.

Hoover, C., and S. Stout. 2007. "The Carbon Consequences of Thinning Techniques: Stand Structure Makes a Difference." *Journal of Forestry* 105 (5): 266–270. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jof/105.5.266>.

Hristov, A. N., J. Oh, C. Lee, R. Meinen, F. Montes, T. Ott, J. Firkins, et al. 2013. "Mitigation of Greenhouse Gas Emissions in Livestock Production – A Review of Technical Options for Non-CO₂ Emissions." *FAO Animal Production and Health Paper No. 177*. Rome: FAO.

Ile, O. J., M. Aguilos, S. Morkoc, J. Heitman, and J. S. King. 2021. "Root Biomass Distribution and Soil Physical Properties of Short-Rotation Coppice American Sycamore (*Platanus Occidentalis* L.) Grown at Different Planting Densities." *Forests* 12 (12): 1806. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f12121806>.

Jackson, R. B., C. W. Cook, J. S. Pippen, and S. M. Palmer. 2009. "Increased Belowground Biomass and Soil CO₂ Fluxes after a Decade of Carbon Dioxide Enrichment in a Warm-Temperate Forest." *ECOLOGY* 90 (12): 3352–66. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-1609.1>.

Jahanzad, Emad, Brent A. Holtz, Cameron A. Zuber, David Doll, Kelsey M. Brewer, Sean Hogan, and Amélie C. M. Gaudin. 2020. "Orchard Recycling Improves Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Potential of Almond Production Systems." *PLOS ONE* 15 (3): e0229588. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229588>.

Jia, S., and T. Akiyama. 2005. "A Precise, Unified Method for Estimating Carbon Storage in Cool-Temperate Deciduous Forest Ecosystems." *AGRICULTURAL AND FOREST METEOROLOGY* 134 (1–4): 70–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2005.08.014>.

Jose, S., S. C. Allen, and P. K. R. Nair. 2008. "Tree-Crop Interactions: Lessons from Temperate Alley-Cropping Systems." In *Ecological Basis of Agroforestry*, edited by D. R. Batish, R. K. Kohli, S. Jose, and H. P. Singh, 15–36. Boca Raton: CRC Press.

Jose, S., A. R. Gillespie, and S. G. Pallardy. 2004. "Interspecific Interactions in Temperate Agroforestry." *Agroforestry Systems* 61: 237–255.

Jose, S., D. Walter, and B. M. Kumar. 2019. "Ecological Considerations in Sustainable Silvopasture Design and Management." *Agroforestry Systems* 93 (6): 2141–2152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-016-0065-2>.

Jose, Shibu, and Andrew M. Gordon, eds. 2008. *Toward Agroforestry Design: An Ecological Approach*. Vol. 4. Advances in Agroforestry. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-6572-9>.

Kargar, A. R., R. MacKenzie, G. P. Asner, and J. van Aardt. 2019. "A Density-Based Approach for Leaf Area Index Assessment in a Complex Forest Environment Using a Terrestrial Laser Scanner." *REMOTE SENSING* 11 (15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11151791>.

Khaleel, Ala' A., Thomas J. Sauer, and John C. Tyndall. 2020. "Changes in Deep Soil Organic Carbon and Soil Properties beneath Tree Windbreak Plantings in the U.S. Great Plains." *Agroforestry Systems* 94 (2): 565–81. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-019-00425-0>.

Kim, D. G., T. M. Isenhardt, T. B. Parkin, R. C. Schultz, and T. E. Loynachan. 2010. "Methane Flux in Cropland and Adjacent Riparian Buffers with Different Vegetation Covers." *Journal of Environmental Quality* 39 (1): 97–105. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2008.0408>.

Klopatek, J. M. 2002. "Belowground Carbon Pools and Processes in Different Age Stands of Douglas-Fir." *Tree Physiology* 22 (2–3): 197–204. <https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/22.2-3.197>.

- Knapp, L. S. P., D. R. Coyle, D. C. Dey, J. S. Fraser, T. Hutchinson, M. A. Jenkins, C. C. Kern, et al. 2023. "Invasive Plant Management in Eastern North American Forests: A Systematic Review." *Forest Ecology and Management* 550: 121517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2023.121517>.
- Körner, C. 2017. "A Matter of Tree Longevity." *Science* 355 (6321): 130–131. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aal2449>.
- Kroll, A. J., J. D. Johnston, T. D. Stokely, and G. W. Meigs. 2020. "From the Ground Up: Managing Young Forests for a Range of Ecosystem Outcomes." *Forest Ecology and Management* 464: 118055. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2020.118055>.
- Lawrence, Nathaniel C., and Steven J. Hall. 2024. "Mechanisms Underlying Episodic Nitrate and Phosphorus Leaching from Poorly Drained Agricultural Soils." *Journal of Environmental Quality* 53 (5): 643–56. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jeq2.20597>.
- Lefebvre, D., A. G. Williams, G. J. D. Kirk, P. J. Burgess, J. Meersmans, M. R. Silman, F. Román-Dañobeytia, J. Farfan, and P. Smith. 2021. "Assessing the Carbon Capture Potential of a Reforestation Project." *SCIENTIFIC REPORTS* 11 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-99395-6>.
- Lekberg, Y., J. D. Bever, R. A. Bunn, R. M. Callaway, M. M. Hart, S. N. Kivlin, J. Klironomos, et al. 2018. "Relative Importance of Competition and Plant–Soil Feedback, Their Synergy, Context Dependency and Implications for Coexistence." *Ecology Letters* 21 (8): 1268–1281. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.13093>.
- Liu, X. W., X. J. Dong, and D. I. Leskovar. 2016. "Ground Penetrating Radar for Underground Sensing in Agriculture: A Review." *INTERNATIONAL AGROPHYSICS* 30 (4): 533–43. <https://doi.org/10.1515/intag-2016-0010>.
- Long, J. N., and G. Vacchiano. 2014. "A Comprehensive Framework of Forest Stand Property–Density Relationships: Perspectives for Plant Population Ecology and Forest Management." *Annals of Forest Science* 71 (3): 325–335. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-013-0351-3>.
- Ma, H., L. Mo, T. W. Crowther, D. S. Maynard, J. van den Hoogen, B. D. Stocker, C. Terrer, and C. M. Zohner. 2021. "The Global Distribution and Environmental Drivers of Aboveground versus Belowground Plant Biomass." *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 5 (8): 1110–1122. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-021-01485-1>.
- Ma, Z., H. Chen, Y. Chen, P. B. Reich, H. Y. H. Chen, X. Zhou, S. Trudeau, et al. 2020. "Combining Remotely Sensed and Field Data to Quantify the Biodiversity-Productivity Relationship in Forests across China." *Global Ecology and Biogeography* 29 (11): 1967–1979. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13145>.
- Major, J. E., K. H. Johnsen, D. C. Barsi, M. Campbell, and J. W. Malcolm. 2013. "Stem Biomass, C and N Partitioning and Growth Efficiency of Mature Pedigreed Black Spruce on Both a Wet and a Dry Site." *FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT* 310 (December): 495–507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2013.08.019>.
- Matthews, A., H. Swan, and K. O'Connor. 2010. "Urine Distribution as a Function of Stocking Rate and Landscape Features in Sheep Grazed Hill Country." In *Proceedings of the New Zealand Grassland Association* 72: 11–16.

Matzek, V., E. S. Gornish, and K. B. Hulvey. 2018. "Emerging Approaches to Successful Ecological Restoration: Five Imperatives to Guide Innovation." *Restoration Ecology* 26 (S2): S110–S113. <https://doi.org/10.1111/avsc.12400>.

MCLAUGHLIN, R. A., E. A. HANSEN, and P. E. POPE. 1987. "BIOMASS AND NITROGEN DYNAMICS IN AN IRRIGATED HYBRID POPLAR PLANTATION." *FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT* 18 (3): 169–88. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-1127\(87\)90159-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-1127(87)90159-9).

Miao, G. F., A. Noormets, M. Gavazzi, B. Mitra, J. C. Domec, G. Sun, S. McNulty, and J. S. King. 2022. "Beyond Carbon Flux Partitioning: Carbon Allocation and Nonstructural Carbon Dynamics Inferred from Continuous Fluxes." *ECOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS* 32 (7). <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2655>.

Morandin, Lora A., and Claire Kremen. 2013. "Hedgerow Restoration Promotes Pollinator Populations and Exports Native Bees to Adjacent Fields." *Ecological Applications* 23 (4): 829–39. <https://doi.org/10.1890/12-1051.1>.

Morkoc, S., M. Aguilos, A. Noormets, K. J. Minick, O. Ile, D. A. Dickey, D. Hardesty, M. Kerrigan, J. Heitman, and J. King. 2022. "Environmental and Plant-Derived Controls on the Seasonality and Partitioning of Soil Respiration in an American Sycamore (*Platanus Occidentalis*) Bioenergy Plantation Grown at Different Planting Densities." *FORESTS* 13 (8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/f13081286>.

Nemeth, D., D. Lamm, C. G. Visser, and M. A. Williams. 2017. "The Effect of Mulch Type on Soil Carbon and Nitrogen Pools in a Field Study Using the DRIFT Spectroscopy Method." *Applied Spectroscopy* 71 (12): 2569–2583.

Norby, R. J., J. M. Warren, C. M. Iversen, A. P. Walker, and J. Childs. 2024. "Getting Allometry Right at the Oak Ridge Free-Air CO₂ Enrichment Experiment: Old Problems and New Opportunities for Global Change Experiments." *PLANTS PEOPLE PLANET* 6 (6): 1480–89. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppp3.10565>.

O'Grady, A. P., D. S. Mendham, K. Mokany, and G. S. Smith. 2024. "Grazing Systems and Natural Capital: Influence of Grazing Management on Natural Capital in Extensive Livestock Production Systems." *Nature-Based Solutions* 4: 100132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbsj.2024.100132>.

Oelebermann, M., R. P. Voroney, N. V. Thevathasan, A. M. Gordon, D. C. Kass, and A. M. Schlönvoigt. 2006. "Soil Carbon Dynamics and Residue Stabilization in a Costa Rican and Southern Canadian Alley Cropping System." *Agroforestry Systems* 68: 27–36.

Ola, A., W. Devos, M. Bouchard, M. J. Mazerolle, P. Raymond, and A. D. Munson. 2024. "Above- and Belowground Carbon Stocks under Differing Silvicultural Scenarios." *Forest Ecology and Management* 558 (April): 121785. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2024.121785>.

Orefice, Joseph, Matthew M. Smith, William C. Weinberg, and Mark Batcheler. 2025. "Carbon Dynamics of Silvopasture Systems in the Northeastern United States." *Scientific Reports* 15 (1): 6995. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-91268-6>.

Osorio, R. J., J. R. Barden, and G. B. Cisar. 2019. "GIS-Based Approach to Estimate Surface Coal Mine Areas and Their Reclamation Status in Southwest Virginia." *Mining, Metallurgy & Exploration* 36 (4): 691–698.

Pallardy, S. G., D. E. Gibbins, and J. L. Rhoads. 2003. "Biomass Production by Two-Year-Old Poplar Clones on Floodplain Sites in the Lower Midwest, USA." *AGROFORESTRY SYSTEMS* 59 (1): 21–26. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026176702075>.

Pellegrini, A. F. A., K. K. McLauchlan, S. E. Hobbie, M. C. Mack, A. L. Marcotte, D. M. Nelson, S. S. Perakis, P. B. Reich, and K. Whittinghill. 2020. "Frequent Burning Causes Large Losses of Carbon from Deep Soil Layers in a Temperate Savanna." *Journal of Ecology* 108 (4): 1426–41. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.13351>.

Pezzopane, J. R. M., M. L. F. Nicodemo, C. Bosi, R. G. Almeida, and S. R. Souza. 2019. "Animal Thermal Comfort Indexes in Silvopastoral Systems with Different Tree Arrangements." *Journal of Thermal Biology* 82: 180–187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtherbio.2019.04.002>.

Pirtel, N. L., R. M. Hubbard, J. B. Bradford, T. E. Kolb, M. E. Litvak, S. R. Abella, S. L. Porter, and M. D. Petrie. 2021. "The Aboveground and Belowground Growth Characteristics of Juvenile Conifers in the Southwestern United States." *Ecosphere* 12 (11): e03839. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.3839>.

Possu, W. B., J. R. Brandle, G. M. Domke, E. C. Schoeneberger, and E. Blankenship. 2004. "Estimating Carbon Storage in Windbreak Trees on U.S. Agricultural Lands." *Agroforestry Systems* 96: 1181–1201.

Pretzsch, H., G. Schütze, and P. Biber. 2017. "Tree Species Mixing Can Increase Maximum Stand Density." *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 48 (4): 396–403. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjfr-2017-0370>.

Refsland, T., J. A. Bennett, J. Karst, et al. 2023. "Plant-Soil Feedback with Implications for Climate-Adaptive Forestry." *Forest Ecology and Management* 529: 120637.

Retzlaff, W. A., J. A. Handest, D. M. O'Malley, S. E. McKeand, and M. A. Topa. 2001. "Whole-Tree Biomass and Carbon Allocation of Juvenile Trees of Loblolly Pine (*Pinus taeda*): Influence of Genetics and Fertilization." *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 31 (6): 960–70. <https://doi.org/10.1139/x01-017>.

Reynolds, P. E., J. A. Simpson, N. V. Thevathasan, and A. M. Gordon. 2007. "Effects of Tree Competition on Corn and Soybean Photosynthesis, Growth, and Yield in a Temperate Tree-Based Agroforestry Intercropping System in Southern Ontario, Canada." *Ecological Engineering* 29 (4): 362–371.

Rheinhardt, R. D., M. C. Rheinhardt, M. M. Brinson, and K. Faser. 2012. "Variation in Forest Canopy Composition of Riparian Networks from Headwaters to Large Rivers: A Multi-Scale Analysis of the Coastal Plain of North Carolina, USA." *Ecological Processes* 1 (1): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1750-0680-7-4>.

Robertson, K. M., and T. L. Hmielowski. 2014. "Effects of Fire Frequency and Season on Resprouting of Woody Plants in Southeastern US Pine-Grassland Communities." *Oecologia* 174 (3): 765–76. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-013-2823-4>.

Salceda-Gonzalez, M. J., M. L. Córdoba, Y. Gao, B. J. Chambers, D. Holden, J. Strock, and R. Koelsch. 2024. "Nutrient Transport through Riparian Buffers: A Comprehensive Meta-Analysis." *Journal of Environmental Management* 351: 118989.

Samuelson, L. J., J. Butnor, C. Maier, T. A. Stokes, K. Johnsen, and M. Kane. 2008. "Growth and Physiology of Loblolly Pine in Response to Long-Term Resource Management: Defining Growth Potential in the Southern United States." *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 38 (4): 721–32. <https://doi.org/10.1139/X07-191>.

Samuelson, L. J., T. A. Stokes, J. R. Butnor, K. H. Johnsen, C. A. Gonzalez-Benecke, P. Anderson, J. Jackson, L. Ferrari, T. A. Martin, and W. P. Cropper. 2014. "Ecosystem Carbon Stocks in Pinus Palustris Forests." *CANADIAN JOURNAL OF FOREST RESEARCH* 44 (5): 476–86. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjfr-2013-0446>.

Samuelson, L. J., T. A. Stokes, J. R. Butnor, K. H. Johnsen, C. A. Gonzalez-Benecke, T. A. Martin, W. P. Cropper, P. H. Anderson, M. R. Ramirez, and J. C. Lewis. 2017. "Ecosystem Carbon Density and Allocation across a Chronosequence of Longleaf Pine Forests." *Ecological Applications* 27 (1): 244–59. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1439>.

Savage, K. E., W. J. Parton, E. A. Davidson, S. E. Trumbore, and S. D. Frey. 2013. "Long-Term Changes in Forest Carbon under Temperature and Nitrogen Amendments in a Temperate Northern Hardwood Forest." *GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY* 19 (8): 2389–2400. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12224>.

Savian, J. V., R. M. T. Schons, D. E. Marchi, D. B. de David, C. Bremm, and P. C. F. Carvalho. 2018. "Rotatinoous Stocking: A Grazing Management Innovation That Mitigates Methane Emissions by Sheep." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 197: 706–715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.06.246>.

Schaedel, M. S., A. J. Larson, D. L. R. Affleck, R. T. Belote, J. M. Goodburn, and D. S. Page-Dumroese. 2017. "Early Forest Thinning Changes Aboveground Carbon Distribution among Pools, but Not Total Amount." *Forest Ecology and Management* 389: 187–198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2016.12.018>.

Schweitzer, C. J. 2019. "History, Highlights, and Perspectives of Southern Upland Hardwood Silviculture Research." *Journal of Forestry* 117 (1): 55–64. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jofore/fvy053>.

Sharrow, S. H., and Syed Ismail. 2004. "Carbon and Nitrogen Storage in Agroforests, Tree Plantations, and Pastures in Western Oregon, USA." *Agroforestry Systems* 60 (2): 123–30. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:AGFO.0000013267.87896.41>.

Smith, J., B. D. Pearce, and M. S. Wolfe. 2021. "Reconciling Productivity with Protection of the Environment: Is Temperate Agroforestry the Answer?" *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems* 28 (1): 80–92.

Steinbeiss, S., H. Beßler, C. Engels, V. M. Temperton, N. Buchmann, C. Roscher, Y. Kreuziger, et al. 2008. "Plant Diversity Positively Affects Short-Term Soil Carbon Storage in Experimental Grasslands." *Global Change Biology* 14 (12): 2937–2949.

Sterck, Frank (F), Marleen (A. E.) Vos, S. Emilia (S. E.) Hannula, Steven (S. P. C.) de Goede, Wim (W) de Vries, Jan (J) den Ouden, Gert-Jan (G. J.) Nabuurs, Wim (W. H) van der Putten, and Ciska (G. F.) Veen. 2021. "Optimizing Stand Density for Climate-Smart Forestry: A Way Forward towards Resilient Forests with Enhanced Carbon Storage under Extreme Climate Events." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 162 (November): 108396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2021.108396>.

Stovall, J. P., T. R. Fox, and J. R. Seiler. 2012. "Short-Term Changes in Biomass Partitioning of Two Full-Sib Clones of *Pinus Taeda* L. under Differing Fertilizer Regimes over 4 Months." *TREES-STRUCTURE AND FUNCTION* 26 (3): 951–61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00468-011-0673-4>.

Stovall et al. 2013. "Allometry Varies among 6-Year-Old *Pinus Taeda* (L.) Clones in the Virginia Piedmont." *FOREST SCIENCE* 59 (1): 50–62. <https://doi.org/10.5849/forsci.10-095>.

Sullivan, B., T. E. Kolb, S. C. Hart, J. P. Kaye, S. Dore, and M. Montes-Helu. 2008. "Thinning Reduces Soil Carbon Dioxide but Not Methane Flux from Southwestern USA Ponderosa Pine Forests." *FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT* 255 (12): 4047–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2008.03.051>.

Sun, Y. B., H. X. Bi, H. S. Xu, H. Q. Duan, R. D. Peng, and J. J. Wang. 2018. "Below-Ground Interspecific Competition of Apple (*Malus Pumila* M.)-Soybean (*Glycine Max* L. Merr.) Intercropping Systems Based on Niche Overlap on the Loess Plateau of China." *SUSTAINABILITY* 10 (9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10093022>.

Sweeney, Bernard W., Stephen J. Czapka, and L. Carol A. Petrow. 2007. "How Planting Method, Weed Abatement, and Herbivory Affect Afforestation Success." *Southern Journal of Applied Forestry* 31 (2): 85–92. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sjaf/31.2.85>.

Tavares, P. A., N. Brites, P. Canhoto, J. A. Santos, and L. M. Rocha. 2019. "Potential of Remote Sensing Applications for Identifying and Monitoring Agroforestry Systems: A Review." *Forests* 10 (3): 200. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f10030200>.

Taylor, B. N., A. E. Strand, E. R. Cooper, K. V. Beidler, M. Schönholz, and S. G. Pritchard. 2014. "Root Length, Biomass, Tissue Chemistry and Mycorrhizal Colonization Following 14 Years of CO₂ Enrichment and 6 Years of N Fertilization in a Warm Temperate Forest." *TREE PHYSIOLOGY* 34 (9): 955–65. <https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/tpu058>.

Thomas, Andrew L., Robert Kallenbach, Thomas J. Sauer, David K. Brauer, David M. Burner, Mark V. Coggeshall, Christian Dold, Wendi Rogers, Sougata Bardhan, and Shibu Jose. 2020. "Carbon and Nitrogen Accumulation within Four Black Walnut Alley Cropping Sites across Missouri and Arkansas, USA." *Agroforestry Systems* 94 (5): 1625–38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-019-00471-8>.

Tian, S. Y., J. F. Cacho, M. A. Youssef, G. M. Chescheir, and J. E. Nettles. 2015. "Switchgrass Growth and Morphological Changes under Established Pine-Grass Agroforestry Systems in the Lower Coastal Plain of North Carolina, United States." *BIOMASS & BIOENERGY* 83 (December): 233–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2015.10.002>.

Tozzini, C., P. Sabbatini, G. Micaelli, A. Battiston, and R. Ibanez. 2015. "Evaluation of Carbon Sequestration in Fruit Orchards: Effects of Biomass Partitioning, Tree Architecture and Orchard Management." *Acta Horticulturae* 1068: 283–290.

Trautwig, A. N., L. G. Eckhardt, N. J. Loewenstein, J. D. Hoeksema, E. A. Carter, and R. L. Nadel. 2017. "Cogongrass (*Imperata Cylindrica*) Affects Above- and Belowground Processes in Commercial Loblolly Pine (*Pinus Taeda*) Stands." *FOREST SCIENCE* 63 (1): 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.5849/forsci.16-016>.

Trettin, C. C., M. F. Jurgensen, M. R. Gale, and J. W. McLaughlin. 2011. "Recovery of Carbon and Nutrient Pools in a Northern Forested Wetland 11 Years after Harvesting and Site Preparation." *FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT* 262 (9): 1826–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2011.07.031>.

Trozso, K. E., J. F. Munsell, W. M. Aust, and J. L. Chamberlain. 2021. "Identifying Potential Forest Farming Sites for Four Medicinal Forest Tree Crops: A Guide to Resource Evaluation." *Journal of Forestry* 119 (3): 294–309. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jofore/fvab023>.

Trugman, A. T., and W. R. L. Anderegg. 2025. "Climate-Dependent Forest Growth: A Global Synthesis." *Nature Climate Change*, forthcoming.

Tufekcioglu, A., J.W. Raich, T.M. Isenhardt, and R.C. Schultz. 2003. "Biomass, Carbon and Nitrogen Dynamics of Multi-Species Riparian Buffers within an Agricultural Watershed in Iowa, USA." *Agroforestry Systems* 57 (3): 187–98. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1024898615284>.

Turnbull, L. A., L. Hector, S. Iles, P. Turnbull, and J. B. W. Hector. 2016. "Understanding the Value of Plant Diversity for Ecosystem Functioning through Niche Theory." *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 283 (1844): 20160536. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2016.0536>.

Tyree, M. C., J. R. Seiler, C. A. Maier, and K. H. Johnsen. 2009. "Pinus Taeda Clones and Soil Nutrient Availability: Effects of Soil Organic Matter Incorporation and Fertilization on Biomass Partitioning and Leaf Physiology." *TREE PHYSIOLOGY* 29 (9): 1117–31. <https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/tpp050>.

Udawatta, R. P., L. Godsey, S. Jose, and P. Motavalli. 2019. "Agroforestry for Sustainability of Smallholder Farming Systems in the Mid-Western USA." *Sustainability* 11 (10): 2879. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11102879>.

Udawatta, R. P., H. E. Garrett, S. Jose, and J. Bollero. 2022. "Effectiveness of Riparian Forest Buffers for Improving Water Quality in Agricultural Watersheds." *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation* 77 (5): 471–480. <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.2022.1028A>.

Udawatta, Ranjith P., Dusty Walter, and Shibu Jose. 2022. "Carbon Sequestration by Forests and Agroforests: A Reality Check for the United States." *Carbon Footprints* 2 (1): N/A-N/A. <https://doi.org/10.20517/cf.2022.06>.

Udawatta, Ranjith P., Pekka Nygren, and Harold E. Garrett. 2005. "Growth of Three Oak Species during Establishment of an Agroforestry Practice for Watershed Protection." *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 35 (3): 602–9. <https://doi.org/10.1139/x04-206>.

Ulyshen, M. D., R. Shefferson, S. Horn, M. K. Taylor, B. Bush, C. Brownie, S. Seibold, and M. S. Strickland. 2017. "Below- and Above-Ground Effects of Deadwood and Termites in Plantation Forests." *Ecosphere* 8 (8): e01910. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.1910>.

Valliant, N. M., A. L. Reiner, and E. K. Noonan-Wright. 2013. "Prescribed Fire Effects on Field-Derived and Simulated Forest Carbon Stocks over Time." *FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT* 310 (December): 711–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2013.09.016>.

- Valverde-Barrantes, O. J., K. A. Smemo, L. M. Feinstein, M. W. Kershner, and C. B. Blackwood. 2018. "Patterns in Spatial Distribution and Root Trait Syndromes for Ecto and Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Temperate Trees in a Mixed Broadleaf Forest." *OECOLOGIA* 186 (3): 731–41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-017-4044-8>.
- Van Mantgem, P. J., A. C. Caprio, N. L. Stephenson, and A. J. Das. 2020. "Forest Restoration and Fuels Reduction Alter Tree Density, Canopy Structure, and Growth in a Dry Western Forest." *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change* 3: 41. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2020.00041>.
- Vargas, R., E. B. Allen, and M. F. Allen. 2009. "Effects of Vegetation Thinning on Above- and Belowground Carbon in a Seasonally Dry Tropical Forest in Mexico." *Biotropica* 41 (3): 302–11. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7429.2009.00494.x>.
- Weedon, J. T., W. K. Cornwell, J. H. C. Cornelissen, A. E. Zanne, C. Wirth, and D. A. Coomes. 2008. "Global Meta-Analysis of Wood Decomposition Rates: A Role for Trait Variation among Tree Species?" *Ecology Letters* 11 (1): 1259–1266. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2008.01259.x>.
- Winford, E. M., and J. C. Gaither. 2012. "Carbon Outcomes from Fuels Treatment and Bioenergy Production in a Sierra Nevada Forest." *Forest Ecology and Management* 282 (October): 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2012.06.041>.
- Xu, S. T., M. L. Silveira, K. S. Inglett, L. E. Sollenberger, and S. Gerber. 2016. "Effect of Land-Use Conversion on Ecosystem C Stock and Distribution in Subtropical Grazing Lands." *PLANT AND SOIL* 399 (1–2): 233–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-015-2690-3>.
- Yang, L., J. Wang, Y. Geng, S. Niu, D. Tian, T. Yan, W. Liu, J. Pan, X. Zhao, and C. Zhang. 2022. "Heavy Thinning Reduces Soil Organic Carbon: Evidence from a 9-Year Thinning Experiment in a Pine Plantation." *CATENA* 211: 106013. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2021.106013>.
- Zamora, D. S., S. Jose, P. K. R. Nair, and C. L. Ramsey. 2006. "Interspecific Competition in a Pecan-Cotton Alleycropping System in the Southern United States: Production Physiology." *Canadian Journal of Botany-Revue Canadienne De Botanique* 84 (11): 1686–94. <https://doi.org/10.1139/B06-130>.
- Zeller, L., H. Pretzsch, and H. Liang. 2018. "Is the Relationship between Species Diversity and Ecosystem Functioning Dependent on the Type of Species Interaction? A System-Level Experiment with 23 Tree Species." *Forests* 9 (6): 333. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f9060333>.
- Zhang, J., H. Zhao, X. Chen, Y. Luo, X. Wen, W. Yang, and Y. Yang. 2024. "The Effect of Thinning on Carbon Dynamics of Chinese Fir (*Cunninghamia lanceolata*) Plantations." *Forest Ecology and Management* 546: 121699. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2024.121699>.
- Zhou, X., Y. Zhou, and M. Zhou. 2014. "Effect of Ridge and Furrow Rainfall Harvesting System on Agroforestry Productivity in Semiarid Loess Hilly Area." *Forest Research* 27: 457–464.
- Zhou, Xinhua, Michele M. Schoeneberger, James R. Brandle, Tala N. Awada, Jianmin Chu, Derrel L. Martin, Jihong Li, Yuqiang Li, and Carl W. Mize. 2015. "Analyzing the Uncertainties in Use of Forest-Derived Biomass Equations for Open-Grown Trees in Agricultural Land." *Forest Science* 61 (1): 144–61. <https://doi.org/10.5849/forsci.13-071>.

3. Appendix A: Literature Review Search Terms and Questions

LITERATURE REVIEW SEARCH TERMS AND QUESTIONS

GENERAL AGROFORESTRY QUESTIONS

Research Question	Search Terms Used
Species Selection Impact on Carbon Accrual	tree OR shrub OR plant species; growth rate OR basal area; carbon OR C; above-ground biomass / tree AND growth rate AND biomass AND (united states or america or usa or u.s) / Physiographic factors / Species; carbon accrual; timber production; agroforestry / Metanalysis OR review
Planting Density Impact on Carbon	tree OR shrub; planting density OR spacing; growth rate; C or Carbon; basal area / Stocking effects / silviculture AND (carbon OR "climate change") AND spacing
Species Diversity and Carbon Relationship	multispecies; multi-species; tree OR shrub OR plant; mixed forest; tree species diversity; partitioning / US or United States or USA / diversity AND tree AND carbon AND (united states or usa or u.s) / Basal area OR carbon / Interspecific partitioning AND carbon OR basal area
Management Strategies for Carbon	silviculture treatment; weed control OR understory control, irrigation, fertigation, pest control; burning; thinning
Belowground Carbon Dynamics	belowground OR below ground; biomass; fine root biomass; root to shoot ratio; above ground biomass to below ground biomass ratio / multispecies; below-ground stratification OR root stratification
System Resilience and Stability	Basal area; hurricane OR derecho OR straight-line wind; disturbance; forest resilience
Establishment Practices and Emissions	Site preparation; forest establishment; mulch*; weed control OR understory control; pest control; invasive species

PRACTICE-SPECIFIC SEARCH TERMS

Conservation Practice	Research Focus	Search Terms Used
Riparian Buffers (391)	Methane emissions from anaerobic soils	Streamside management zone* OR riparian buffer; methane OR CH4; restore*; periodic flood*
Wood-Product Systems	Thinning and harvest strategies	Basal area; hurricane OR derecho OR straight-line wind; disturbance; forest resilience, thinning
All Practices	General resilience and disturbance recovery	Forest resilience

LAND MANAGER OBJECTIVE-SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

Objective Category	Research Focus	Key Terms
Conservation-Oriented	Tree planting impacts on grasslands/wetlands	Conservation outcomes; wildlife habitat; grassland; wetland
Livestock-Focused	Shade/shelter characteristics and fodder quality	Shade; shelter; forage productivity; animal nutrition
Timber/Bioenergy	Sustainable harvest and mitigation balance	Timber stand improvement; commercial thinning; harvest rotation
Tree Crops/NTFP	Low-emission production systems	Tree crops; non-timber forest products; nitrogen management

BROAD OVERARCHING TERMS

Category	Terms
Geographic Limiters	US OR United States OR USA OR u.s OR america
Carbon-Related	carbon OR C; carbon sequestration; greenhouse gas; GHG; climate change
Tree/Plant Terms	tree OR shrub OR plant; woody; forest; agroforestry
Research Type	meta-analysis OR review; systematic review

NOTES ON SEARCH STRATEGY

- **Time Period Focus:** 2000-2025 for most current research
- **Geographic Focus:** Primarily United States and temperate regions
- **Study Types:** Prioritized peer-reviewed articles, meta-analyses, and systematic reviews
- **Exclusions:** Tropical systems unless specifically applicable to temperate agroforestry
- **Language:** English-language publications

4. Appendix B: Science Recommendations

CRITICAL RESEARCH GAPS

- **Carbon Dynamics.** Our review reveals significant knowledge gaps concerning carbon dynamics in agroforestry systems. There is a dearth of longitudinal studies which have investigated dynamics over periods greater than ~25 years, which limits our ability to synthesize across longer time horizons and across practice-specific contexts.
- **Belowground Carbon.** Research suggests belowground carbon represents 20-40% of total carbon pools, but measurement techniques and understanding of root morphology effects on carbon accrual remain limited. Studies indicate ectomycorrhizal tree species may provide superior belowground carbon benefits, but more work is needed on these topics to better understand these dynamics.
- **Species Interactions.** Species diversity and functional composition represent another important research frontier. Current evidence indicates that mixed-species stands demonstrate increased productivity due to niche complementarity, potentially enhancing carbon sequestration. However, the relationship between functional diversity and carbon outcomes requires further investigation, particularly regarding optimal species combinations for different geographic regions.

GHG QUANTIFICATION

- **System boundary definition.** The field would benefit greatly from consistent methodologies for defining system boundaries in carbon accounting across agroforestry practices. Clear distinction between direct on-farm impacts and indirect effects would facilitate more accurate comparisons. Additionally, establishing standard metrics for comparing carbon benefits across different practices (windbreaks, silvopasture, alley cropping) would enable practitioners and policy makers to make more informed decisions.

MEASUREMENT, DATA COLLECTION, AND DATA ACCESS

- **New measurement technologies.** Traditional field measurements rely heavily on allometric equations developed for forestry, which may not accurately capture the unique conditions found in agroforestry systems (i.e. greater sun exposure). Encouragingly, new technologies like LiDAR and photogrammetry are improving accessibility, transparency, and accuracy of carbon measurements, though their application in agroforestry contexts remains limited, and more testing is needed to determine context-specific fidelity. Currently, there is no prescriptive approach to measuring biomass accumulation which factors in context, specific practices, location, size, accuracy requirements, etc.
- **Longitudinal datasets.** A significant challenge is the scarcity of longitudinal datasets for agroforestry systems, particularly those measuring belowground carbon and full GHG accounting.
- **Standardization of tree metrics.** Substantial variability exists in how tree metrics are collected, reported, and converted to carbon estimates, which further complicates synthesis. Standardized protocols would enable more meaningful comparisons across studies and practices.
- **Standardization of management practice reporting.** Inconsistent reporting of management practices (such as pruning, thinning, fertilization) limits our understanding of how management interventions affect carbon outcomes in the long term.

MODELING

- **The USDA's COMET-Farm platform.** This is a valuable tool for predicting biomass carbon accumulation in agroforestry systems, but our analysis reveals important accuracy challenges. COMET tends to overpredict carbon in young plantings (under 15 years) and high-density plantings (over 1000 trees/hectare), with some error rates exceeding 400%. For mature plantings with moderate density, COMET provides slightly conservative estimates, suggesting this tool is most reliable for established systems with conventional planting densities.
- **Future modeling efforts** should focus on incorporating management interventions (thinning, pruning) and their effects on carbon storage, and intercomparison between models. Models that better represent belowground carbon dynamics, including root lifespan and mycorrhizal associations, are also needed, along with agroforestry-specific models which are able to capture the specific conditions. Additionally, integrating albedo effects into carbon models is important, particularly for high-latitude regions where reduced albedo from coniferous trees may partially offset carbon sequestration benefits.
- **Producer decision-support tools.** At the farm scale, producers would benefit from accessible decision-support tools that help select optimal agroforestry practices based on site conditions, climate, and management objectives. These tools should integrate carbon accounting with other ecosystem services and economic returns to support comprehensive planning that aligns climate goals with livelihood needs.

OVERARCHING AGROFORESTRY SCIENCE

RECOMMENDATIONS AND IMPLEMENTATION TIMELINE

- We recommend leveraging USDA conservation practice implementation data to create a national database of agroforestry carbon outcomes across diverse regions and practices. Developing

agroforestry-specific carbon protocols that account for the unique characteristics of these systems compared to forests or agricultural lands alone would improve measurement accuracy.

- Implementation should proceed in phases, beginning with standardizing carbon measurement protocols for agroforestry practices and improving model accuracy within 1-2 years. Medium-term goals (2-5 years) should include establishing a network of demonstration sites with consistent monitoring and developing integrated decision-support tools. Long-term efforts (5+ years) should focus on quantifying the full GHG balance of mature agroforestry systems and refining best practices for optimizing climate benefits while supporting other ecosystem services and producer goals.

5. Appendix C: Key Findings

KEY SCIENCE FINDINGS

SPECIES DIVERSITY AND COMPOSITION DRIVE CARBON BENEFITS

- **Mixed-species tree plantings can enhance carbon sequestration** through complementary resource use, but must be balanced against management complexity. Agroforestry systems already provide diversity benefits over single land uses, and modest increases in tree species diversity (2-5 species) can optimize both carbon outcomes and practical management.
- **Optimal carbon outcomes require balancing fast and slow-growing species** - fast-growing pioneers provide rapid initial carbon sequestration while slow-growing, dense-wood species with deep root systems and ectomycorrhizal associations ensure long-term carbon storage and system durability.

PLANTING DENSITY SHOWS NON-LINEAR RELATIONSHIPS

- **Intermediate planting densities maximize carbon sequestration**, not maximum densities. Excessive density ultimately reduces growth due to competition and resource limitations.
- **Tree-wise mixing of species yields higher productivity than segregated plantings**, demonstrating that spatial arrangement significantly influences carbon outcomes.

MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES CAN ENHANCE OR UNDERMINE CARBON GOALS

- **Partial-cutting and selective harvest maintain significantly higher carbon stocks** than clear-cutting while still producing wood products. Forest conversion through moderate thinning can enhance carbon sequestration when properly executed.
- **Site preparation and fertilization methods substantially impact carbon balance** - intensive tillage can cause net carbon losses during establishment, while excessive nitrogen inputs increase nitrous oxide emissions regardless of source.

PRACTICE TYPE MATTERS LESS THAN IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

- **Carbon outcomes are not determined by agroforestry practice type** (windbreak vs. silvopasture vs. alley cropping) but rather by site conditions, species selection, planting density, and management decisions.
- **Belowground carbon represents 20-40% of total forest carbon** and varies significantly by tree species. Some conifers and deep-rooted species allocate more carbon to roots and soil, enhancing long-term carbon storage in more stable soil pools.

KEY TECHNICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

SPECIES SELECTION AND SYSTEM DESIGN

- Select tree species based on site conditions, functional traits, and carbon storage potential rather than just growth rate. **Combine fast-growing pioneers with long-lived, dense-wood species** to optimize both rapid carbon accumulation and long-term storage.
- **Design systems with 2-5 complementary tree species** planted intermixed rather than in separate blocks, balancing diversity benefits with management complexity. Include both fast-growing pioneers and long-lived species for immediate and sustained carbon benefits.

ESTABLISHMENT AND DENSITY MANAGEMENT

- **Use intermediate planting densities** (varies by practice: 100-400 trees/hectare for silvopasture, up to 1000+ for windbreaks) rather than maximum densities to optimize long-term carbon sequestration.
- **Minimize soil disturbance during establishment** through reduced tillage, spot preparation, and maintaining existing vegetation between rows to protect existing carbon stocks.

MANAGEMENT FOR CLIMATE MITIGATION

- **Implement rotational grazing in silvopasture systems** to enhance soil carbon retention and reduce methane emissions per unit of animal output while improving forage quality.
- **Retain woody debris on-site through mulching or controlled decomposition** rather than burning to minimize emissions and enhance soil organic matter development.
- **Use nitrogen inputs judiciously regardless of source** (synthetic fertilizer, manure, or nitrogen-fixing plants) as all can increase nitrous oxide emissions that offset carbon benefits.